

D4.9

Concept and impact validation for the case-study buildings based on the virtual test-bed

Authors: **UGent, KU Leuven, EK**

Date: **February 2021 (M54)**

Version: 1.0

Dissemination level: Public

Lead beneficiary: DTU (Technical University of Denmark, DK)

Deliverable lead: UGent (Ghent University, Belgium)

Author(s): UGent (Ghent University, Belgium)

Josué Borrajo Bastero

Eline Himpe (eline.himpe@ugent.be)

KU Leuven (Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium)

Iago Cupeiro Figueroa

Damien Picard

EK (Energoklastr, Czech Republic)

Lukas Ferkl

Reviewer(s): UGent (Ghent University, Belgium)

Jelle Laverge

Deliverable history: Version 1.0: February 2021 (M54)

Dissemination level: Public

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5110294>

Summary

The objective of work package 4 is to validate the hybridGEOTABS concept by assessing its impact/performance, using a selection of demonstration and case-study buildings. In this deliverable, the performance of the hybridGEOTABS concept is assessed by quantifying the savings obtained by using hybridGEOTABS combined with Rule Based Controls and Model Predictive Controls, instead of more traditional heating/cooling and control strategies. This quantification is done using dynamic building energy simulations of case-study buildings in a virtual test-bed. The deliverable documents the methodology, analysis and resulting conclusions of this assessment.

In task 4.3 a virtual test-bed was developed, consisting of emulator models for each of the case-study buildings. The selection of case-study buildings is documented in D4.1-2 and their architectural and technical properties are documented in D4.4. The case-study buildings include one building for each of the four building typologies that is studied in the project: an office building (Infrax building, BE), a school¹ (Libeznice school, CZ), a multi-family building (Haus M, CH) and an elderly home (Ter Potterie, BE). For each of these, a dynamic building energy simulation model is developed in the Modelica simulation environment, as documented in D4.7. In addition to and starting from this model representing the as-built situation of the building (*hybridGEOTABS_AB*), different scenarios are developed for the heating and cooling systems and control (see D4.3). The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (see D4.5) allows to quantify the savings obtained by applying GEOTABS to a building through a comparison of its performance with the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline. Finally, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario, by comparison to the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline, allows to quantify the savings obtained by the new model predictive controllers developed in the project. Figure o-1 provides an overview and reading guide of the WP4 deliverables. The energy, environmental and cost performance results discussed in this report, are complemented with results based on real-life measurements in D4.12.

Figure o-1: Overview of WP4 deliverables – Reading guide

¹ Remark that the simulations of the Libeznice school model were not finalised in time and are therefore not included in this report.

From the energy and environmental analysis of the simulated case-study buildings, we can conclude that in all case-study buildings the hybridGEOTABS scenarios achieve lower primary energy use than the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline scenario, and the use of MPC leads to additional savings when compared to RBC. The hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario is able to achieve up to 48% of primary energy savings and 62% of CO₂-emission savings for the Haus M multi-family building. In that building, about 95% of the space heating demand and 45% of the space cooling demand are covered by GEOTABS. For the Infrac office building and Ter Potterie elderly home, the reductions achieved in the hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario are smaller, that is around 6% and 9% of primary energy savings, and 27% and 14% of CO₂-emission savings respectively. In these buildings, about 37% of the heating demands and over 80% of the cooling demands are covered by GEOTABS. However, the Infrac office building illustrates the significant improvements (38% of additional primary energy and CO₂-emission savings) possible by use of MPC, leading up to 42% primary energy savings and 54% of CO₂-emission savings when comparing hybridGEOTABS-MPC to nonGEOTABS-RBC. The improved system control leads to an increase in the share of GEOTABS in heating and an increase in overall system efficiencies (e.g. reduced electricity use of the fans, increased SCOP of the heat pump, and overall system efficiencies).

In the Ter Potterie elderly home, at the first glance, the savings due to MPC are limited to about 3% of primary energy savings. However, considering that the MPC in that building was not allowed the same degrees of freedom as in the Infrac building, this result is not unexpected. When focussing on those parts of the system where the MPC was allowed to make a difference compared to the RBC, primary energy savings up to 21% were observed. In summary, the performance of the hybridGEOTABS system is highly influenced by the specific HVAC configuration (what part of the heating load can be covered by the GSHP) and the degrees of freedom of the controls.

The aforementioned results all assume that the electricity provided to the building represents the EU average electricity mix in 2020 (primary energy conversion factor of 2.0 and 260 gCO₂/kWh). The report also includes results with the local electricity mix from the country where the building is located, and a sensitivity analysis. This analysis illustrates that hybridGEOTABS buildings benefit more from an increased energy-efficiency and reduced carbon-intensity of the electricity mix. Therefore, their advantage as compared to nonGEOTABS buildings will only increase in the future.

Regarding the life-cycle cost calculations for these buildings, it was found that the hybridGEOTABS-MPC scenarios lead to an increase in life-cycle cost when compared to the nonGEOTABS-RBC, but this increase is limited to between 1% and 4%, which seems a small amount, especially for providing a much more environmentally friendly and comfortable building.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

<i>AB</i>	As-built
<i>AHU</i>	Air Handling Unit
<i>ASHP</i>	Air Source Heat Pump
<i>BE</i>	Belgium
<i>CapEX</i>	Capital Expenditures
<i>CBA</i>	Cost-Benefit Analysis
<i>CH</i>	Switzerland
<i>CZ</i>	Czech Republic
<i>COP</i>	Coefficient of Performance
<i>CO₂</i>	Carbon Dioxide
<i>DX.Y</i>	Deliverable X.Y, where X and Y are natural numbers.
<i>DHW</i>	Domestic Hot Water
<i>EER</i>	Energy Efficiency Ratio
<i>FCU</i>	Fan Coil Unit
<i>GSHP</i>	Ground Source Heat Pump
<i>HVAC</i>	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
<i>HEX</i>	Heat exchanger
<i>IDEAS</i>	Integrated District Energy Assessment Simulation
<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicator
<i>MPC</i>	Model Predictive Control
<i>NPV</i>	Net Present Value (value affected by discount rate)
<i>OpEX</i>	Operational Expenditures
<i>ppm</i>	Parts per million
<i>RBC</i>	Rule-based Control
<i>RMOT</i>	Running Mean Outdoor Temperature
<i>SCOP</i>	Seasonal Coefficient of Performance
<i>SEER</i>	Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio
<i>TABS</i>	Thermally Active Building System
<i>Teq</i>	Equivalent Outdoor temperature
<i>TMY</i>	Typical Meteorological Year

Symbols

θ_{rm}	Running Mean Outdoor Temperature [°C]
θ_{ed-i}	Mean Outdoor Temperature i -day before the present day [°C], $\{i \in \mathbb{N} : 1 \leq i \leq 7\}$

1. Introduction

In this deliverable, the performance of the hybridGEOTABS concept is assessed by quantifying the savings obtained by using hybridGEOTABS as such and combined with using Model Predictive Controls, instead of more traditional heating/cooling and control strategies. This quantification is done using dynamic building energy simulations (BES) in a virtual test-bed.

This introduction sets out the case-study buildings and scenarios for which emulator models are made. In chapters 2 and 3, the methodology and the modelling approach are explained, documenting how the models are conceived to allow a comparison between the different scenarios (set-up of this theoretical experiment), and how the outputs are calculated. In chapters 4-7, for each of the case-study buildings, the behaviour of the building in the simulations is documented and the outcomes of the analysis are presented. In chapter 8, the results are summarized for all case-study buildings and scenarios, leading to the general conclusions of the concept and impact validation effort.

1.1. Case-study buildings

The case-study buildings are:

- 1) Haus M multi-family building in Zürich (CH)
- 2) Elementary School building in Libeznice (CZ)
- 3) Ter Potterie Elderly home in Bruges (BE)
- 4) Infrac/Fluvius office building in Dilbeek (BE)

A summary of the building properties is given in this deliverable, in the introductory parts of chapters 4-7. For a detailed technical documentation of the buildings (incl. floor plans, hydraulic schemes, operation modes, controls etc.), the reader is referred to [D4.11](#).

Figure 1-1: Pictures of the case-study buildings (top: Infrac, Libeznice School, bottom: Haus M, Ter Potterie)

1.2. Original emulator models

The emulator models are made in Modelica [1], an object-oriented equation-based simulation environment that is suited for multi-disciplinary systems and includes libraries for building energy systems. The models of the buildings are composed of components from the libraries IDEAS [2], Modelica Standard Library [3] and Buildings [4]. A component is a model of a certain phenomenon. It is a predefined piece of code in Modelica language represented by a graphical element. A component can be reproduced one or several times and can be combined with other components to build a model of a certain system, by dragging, dropping and connecting the various components. The components can be the model of a boiler, the model of a wall, the model of a heating curve, the model of a PID, the model of a Boolean operator, etc. The libraries are ordered collections of several components.

The As-Built (AB) scenarios *hybridGEOTABS_AB* are the models corresponding as good as possible to the real case-study buildings, including their specific HVAC-systems, system settings and controls. These models were made first and allow a comparison with the measurements in the original real-life buildings, and these measurements are also used to calibrate the emulator models. The models are documented and included in [D4.7](#).

1.3. Scenarios

hybridGEOTABS refers to the combination of GEOTABS with secondary heating/cooling systems, controlled by use of Model Predictive Controls (MPC). The validation of the concept takes place by comparing the performance of *hybridGEOTABS* to reference or baseline scenarios. In order to clearly distinguish the (full) concept from the scenarios, it is also called *hybridGEOTABS-MPC*.

The first reference scenario is a hybrid GEOTABS building with a common rule-based type of control (RBC). This scenario is called *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and represents the current GEOTABS building practice. Secondly, *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* and *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* are compared to *nonGEOTABS-RBC*, representing a traditional building with a more traditional and non-renewable type of heating and cooling system instead of GEOTABS, and controlled by a common RBC. The scenarios *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC* are thus the baseline scenarios to which *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* is compared. The HVAC in these baseline scenarios was designed in such a way that it allows to climatise buildings everywhere in Europe, including warm, moderate and colder climates. So the baseline HVAC-concepts are the same for each case-study building (see [D4.5](#)). The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario is developed for three case-study buildings that are also demonstration building in the project (Infrac/Fluvius, Ter Potterie and Libeznice school). The MPC is designed in the same way as the actual MPC implemented in the demonstration buildings. It is documented in [D4.11](#).

An overview of the different case-study buildings and scenarios for which an emulator is made, is given in **Erro Non se atopa a orixe da referencia..** The As-Built scenarios *hybridGEOTABS_AB* are the models corresponding to the original buildings with their original controls.

Table 1-1: Overview of scenarios for the virtual test bed

Case-study building	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS_AB	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Haus M Multi-family	X	X	X (RBC)	NA
Libeznice school	X	X	X (MPC)	X
Infrac office	X	X	X (RBC)	X
Ter Potterie Elderly home	X	X	X (MPC)	X

2. Methodology: models

In order to allow for a good comparison between the different scenarios and cases, some modelling assumptions need to be aligned: indoor climate (thermal comfort model), outdoor climate (reference years), HVAC systems (baseline systems), control systems and other modelling parameters. These parameters and assumptions are discussed in this section.

2.1. Scenarios

The scheme in Figure 2-1 illustrates the different scenarios occurring in the virtual test-bed. In Table 1-1: Overview of scenarios for the virtual test bed the scenarios for each specific case-study building are listed. The *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario is a model that represents the building “as built” and is documented in [D4.7](#). The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* baselines have the same building envelope and HVAC-systems as the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* model. An exception is the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* model of Haus M, which has been modified in comparison to the as built scenario to include floor cooling and a secondary heating and cooling system (explained in section 4.1.3). The differences between the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* and the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenarios are in the controls, the thermal comfort boundaries and the use of reference weather conditions. The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline also uses the same building envelope as the “as built” scenarios, but the HVAC-system is replaced by a more traditional HVAC-solution and a baseline RBC. Deliverable [D4.5](#) defines the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* and *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline concepts. The next sections provide an overview of these baseline concepts. The detailed specifications of the baselines and the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* for each of the case-study building models is explained in [D4.7](#).

Figure 2-1: Scheme showing the different scenarios for the case-study buildings

2.1.1. nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline

The model of the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline involves the substitution of all the HVAC- systems in the models of every case-study building. This includes the ventilation system and the heating and cooling systems. The hybridGEOTABS HVAC is thus replaced by the more traditional nonGEOTABS HVAC. The original hybridGEOTABS HVAC components are replaced by common, validated HVAC-components that are included in the Modelica libraries 'IDEAS'[1] and 'Buildings' [4]. The baseline is composed by the following elements:

- 1) Fan coil unit (FCU) in each conditioned zone (heating and cooling).
- 2) Gas boiler for heating production (natural gas as the energy source).
- 3) Chiller (air as the heat sink).
- 4) Air-to-air heat exchanger (heat recovery) in the air handling unit.
- 5) Control based on comfort limits defined in the EN16798 standard.

Figure 2-2: General schematics for the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline

Figure 2-2 represents a schematic of the HVAC in the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline. The fan coil units take the heat from the gas boiler when the zone requires heating and release the heat to the chiller when the zone requires cooling. The boiler and the chiller are activated as soon as any zone requires heating or cooling, respectively. Each conditioned zone has an independent control that selects the operation mode of each FCU based on the operative temperature (OT) of the zone, the comfort limits applied and the running mean outdoor temperature (RMOT). The operative temperature is defined as the average of the air and radiative temperatures in the centre of the zone. The comfort limits are dynamic, which means that they change depending on the value of one or several parameters. In this case, the running mean outdoor temperature (RMOT) is the only parameter (see also section 2.2). The independent control by zone allows to have heating and cooling in different zones at the same time. The ventilation system includes an air-to-air heat exchanger to recover the heat from the extracted air during the heating period. The same heat exchanger can work during the cooling period, cooling down the fresh air when its temperature is higher than the extracted air. The effect of the heat recovery comprises the whole building and it may conflict with the heating and/or cooling needs of each individual zones.

2.1.2. *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline

Figure 2-3 represents a schematic view of the basic configuration of a *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* system. The most relevant elements are:

- Thermally Activated Building System (TABS) (heating and cooling).
- Ground Source Heat Pump (GSHP) (heating and cooling).
- Heat exchanger (passive cooling from the borefield).
- Control based on comfort limits defined in the norm EN16798
- Secondary emission system (heating and/or cooling, if required). This element varies depending on the original building specifications.
- Secondary system heat source/sink (heating and/or cooling, if required). This element varies depending on the original building specifications.
- Air-to-air heat exchanger (heat recovery) in the air handling unit.

Figure 2-3: General schematics for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline

This scheme is also valid for *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* system, which differs only in the type of control.

Detailed information about the baselines and their controls can be found in [D4.7](#).

2.2. Indoor and outdoor climate

2.2.1. Outdoor climate

The case-study buildings were designed for their specific climate, and thus in the simulations the climate of their original location is used. The as built models were validated with the weather data corresponding to the measured parameters of each building (see D4.7). For the study in this deliverable, the weather conditions are defined by the typical climate year for the case-specific location.

The typical meteorological year (TMY) is a representative year of a certain weather station based on hourly observations over multiple years. It is a 365-day year generated with the average values of a long-term series of measured data of a specific location combined with estimations of other parameters that are incomplete or missing. The considered parameters include global solar radiation, sky coverage, barometric pressure, dry-bulb and dew point temperatures and other parameters that may be relevant. The models for Haus M, Ter Potterie, Infrac and Libeznice school use the typical meteorological year provided by the software Meteonorm, which produced a typical meteorological year based on collected data between the years 2000 and 2009. The weather files are in TMY3 format, with small technical adaptations to be used in the respective building models.

2.2.2. Thermal comfort and CO₂-concentration limits

The comfort can be defined as the level of satisfaction of a person with the environment he or she is in in a certain moment. Many aspects influence comfort, such as temperature, moisture, intensity of light, level of noise or the movement of the air. This part of the project focuses on two aspects relevant in the scope of this deliverable. On one hand, maintaining a minimum level of air quality, represented by a maximum CO₂-concentration in the zones, which imposes a minimum flowrate in the ventilation system. On the other hand, maintaining a minimum level of thermal comfort through the control of the indoor temperature, which activates the heating or cooling depending on the operative temperature of the zones.

Some aspects of a comfortable indoor climate, such as the CO₂-concentration, can be achieved easily with some static controls. For the thermal comfort, the control should not be based on a constant limit, since the people perceive their thermal comfort as the combination of several effects that vary along the year, and may be comfortable in a range of operative temperatures. A good approximation of the thermal comfort for the majority of the people is defined in the standard EN16798-1 (*Energy performance of buildings - Ventilation for buildings - Part 1: Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics - Module M1-6*). This European Standard defines the indoor boundary conditions to assess the energy performance of different types of buildings. This is therefore the appropriate way to set the parameters of the different models to make a suitable comparison between them. In other words, for the same kind of building all the baselines will work under the same boundary conditions, which are considered optimal in terms of comfort. In the standard, the thermal comfort is defined by dynamic thermal boundaries based on the Running Mean Outdoor Temperature (RMOT). This parameter tries to reflect the effect due to thermal inertia of the objects in the space as well as the adaptation of the occupants to outdoor climate and it actually relaxes the constraints on the measured temperatures. A direct consequence is that an isolated hot or cold day will have less influence on the thermal comfort-based control. The previous days will have also some influence in the boundaries that are imposed on the operative temperature. There are different ways for the calculation of the RMOT, but the Standard defines the following one:

$$\theta_{rm} = \frac{\theta_{ed-1} + 0.8 \cdot \theta_{ed-2} + 0.6 \cdot \theta_{ed-3} + 0.5 \cdot \theta_{ed-4} + 0.4 \cdot \theta_{ed-5} + 0.3 \cdot \theta_{ed-6} + 0.2 \cdot \theta_{ed-7}}{3.8}$$

Where θ_{rm} is the RMOT of the present day in °C and every term θ_{ed-i} is the mean outdoor temperature in °C of the i -day before the present day.

Based on the RMOT, the comfort range for a certain RMOT temperature is given for several types of buildings with two soft constraints for the operative temperature of the zone (T_{up_soft} and T_{down_soft}). The range indicates the values for the temperature where the thermal comfort is optimal. The combination of all comfort ranges along the RMOT creates the comfort band, which defines the optimal operative temperature. As the constraints are soft, there are acceptable violations of the comfort band under certain conditions. The maximum acceptable deviation from the soft constraints is also described in the standard. With that deviation it is possible to define the hard constraints (T_{up_hard} and T_{down_hard}). The operative temperature must never go higher than the T_{up_hard} nor lower than the T_{down_hard} limits. Figure 2-4 presents the indoor operative temperature limits in function of the RMOT, for the various case-study building typologies. More information on thermal comfort limits is also found in [D5.2](#).

**LIMITS EN16798
(HAUS M)**

**OFFICES AND SCHOOLS
(INFRAX AND LIBEZNICE)**

**ELDERLY HOMES
(TER POTERIE)**

Figure 2-4: Comfort limits for Haus M, Infrax, Libeznice school and Ter Potterie

As mentioned before, some violations of the constraints are allowed. To determine those violations four kinds of cumulative penalties are calculated for each zone:

- If the operative temperature is in the comfort band, the penalties are null.
- If the operative temperature is between any soft limit and its respective hard limit, the penalty is calculated as the integral of the deviation of the operative temperature from the soft limit with respect to the time. As a result there are two penalties, one for soft underheating and one for soft overheating.
- If the value of the operative temperature passes the hard limits, the overheating and underheating penalties consist of the integral of the deviation of the operative temperature from the hard limit with respect to the time.

The calculations for all penalties are the same:

$$penalty_{lim,i} = \int_0^{8760} |OT_i - T_{lim}| \cdot dt$$

Where OT_i is the operative temperature in the zone i in °C, T_{lim} represents the four kinds of limits in °C and the time is in hours. The units of the penalty, consequently, are in °C·h (degrees·hour). If the integration is calculated for a period of a year (8760 hours) then it is possible to refer the penalties as °C·h/year (degrees·hour/year).

Every model has its own controls for heating and cooling, but all of them are evaluated using the described comfort limits. Therefore, all comfort limits were included in a Modelica component. This component is included in the models (Figure 2-5). This component also calculates the mentioned penalties, which are valuable outputs for adjustments in the control or in other components. Every conditioned zone has an independent control that tries to set the operative temperature of the zone between two temperature limits given by the limits T_{up_soft} and T_{down_soft} .

Figure 2-5: Indoor temperature component

The penalties were used by the modellers to adjust the control of the models to get good results nevertheless, the actual value of the penalties is not discussed in the deliverable since the interest of this text is focused on the energy analysis.

Not all conditioned zones are subjected to the explained thermal comfort conditions, since not all of them are designed to be occupied and therefore their comfort level is not monitored. The non-monitored zones are staircases, corridors, photocopy rooms and similar zones that have only sporadic presence of people or are used as transition zones. The toilets are always included in the analysis.

Furthermore, if a building has a setback program, the comfort conditions are only taken into account during the normal use of the building, so any violation of thermal comfort during periods of setback is neglected.

3. Methodology: key performance indicators

For the different cases and scenarios, Key Performance Indicators (KPI) are calculated to evaluate and compare their energy, environmental and cost performance. In this section, the methodology and system boundaries of these estimations are explained that will be used in the virtual test-bed. In the following sections the performance indicators for energy, environmental and cost performance are described. In the analysis in the virtual test-bed we will focus mainly on the KPIs related to the core elements of the hybridGEOTABS concept, that is the heating and cooling functions.

3.1. Energy and Environmental performance indicators

The energy and environmental performance indicators include indicators related to the energy use and energy efficiency, the use of renewable energy sources (including geothermal energy) and the environmental impact related to the energy use. In general, the *EN ISO 52000:2017* standards series on 'Energy Performance of Buildings – Overarching EPB assessment' is used as a guideline throughout the performance analysis in this project. For example, in EN ISO 52000-1 the general framework and procedures are set out, including terminology and definitions. Within this framework, methodological decisions are made in function of the scope and objectives of this report and project. For example, the focus of the analysis is on the HVAC of the building, that is modelled in detail in the virtual test-bed.

3.1.1. Component, system and building level

Figure 3-1: The different levels and the highlighted aspects included in the energy KPI

The performance indicators may be defined at three different levels: the components, systems and building level. The **energy use and energy-efficiency** can be calculated at each of the three aforementioned levels. On one hand, the instant values of the performance indicators use the instant power and provide insight in the instantaneous performance of the system. On the other hand, by integrating the power through time, information about energy use and efficiency are obtained.

Component level

The component level is the basic level, documenting the performance of individual components in the energy system. It can consider all components in the HVAC of the building that have a relevant impact regarding the energy transformations or energy transfers in the building, for example: heat pumps, pumps, fans, boilers and other devices. In this group, some components, such as valves, counters, sensors and similar devices which have

a very low energy use, are neglected, and the focus is on the key components in the heating and cooling systems, in this case especially on the heat pump.

System level

This level includes the various systems in the building that provide building services (or functions) to the building. In the EN ISO 52000-series on the Energy Performance of Buildings, the services are categorised as follows:

- Heating (HEAT)
- Cooling (COOL)
- Ventilation (VENT)
- Domestic hot water (DHW)
- Lighting (LIGHT)
- Humidification
- Dehumidification
- Other services
- Building automation and control (BAC)
- Photovoltaics (PV)
- Wind

The Other services include appliances (e.g. computers, cooking equipment, television...), transportation devices (e.g. lift) etc. Sometimes also the latter three services listed above are included. In the virtual test-bed, the focus is on heating, cooling and ventilation. The other systems are not modelled in detail in the virtual test-bed.

A system is, based on this categorisation, than a combination of a set of components for energy conversion, storage, distribution and emission that together provide a service to the building (heating system, cooling system...). A component can belong to various services (e.g. heat pump providing both heating and cooling and DHW services), several combinations of components can form subsystems to serve the same services (e.g. primary and secondary heating systems in hybrid systems). In such cases, in order to be able to split the performance indicators for heating and cooling and consider a correct amount of energy for each service, one can think of the entire system being in different 'operation modes' (heating mode, cooling mode) dependent on the time. The energy use for each service can then be split according to the operation mode. Therefore, for the calculation of KPI at the system level, a thorough understanding of the building systems and controls is required.

Building level

The indicators at the building level are useful to compare the energy performance with other buildings of the same kind. They also reflect the energetic interactions with the surroundings, such as the ground or the electric grid. Figure 3-2 depicts the assessment boundaries at the building level, according to EN ISO 52000-1. At the building level, the *energy need* is energy delivered to all the systems in the building for the various services under consideration (thus it is the 'final' energy for all the systems). This is depicted by boundary 'a' in Figure 3-2, that is the assessment boundary through which energy is imported or exported, which is quantified at the building level. The *energy delivered* thus comes from outside this assessment boundary. It is the energy from on-site energy sources (e.g. the output from photovoltaic or wind energy systems, the heat output of the underground...) and the energy from off-site sources. The latter are categorised as nearby off-site sources (e.g. a district heating system) and distant off-site sources (e.g. electricity grid, natural gas grid...). In real-life buildings, the energy from off-site sources is typically metered. This is also the typical assessment level that is referred to in the assessment of primary energy, greenhouse gas emissions and energy costs.

Key

- | | | | |
|----|--|---|--|
| a | assessment boundary (use energy balance) | 1 | PV, solar |
| b | perimeter: on-site | 2 | wind |
| c | perimeter: nearby | 3 | boiler room |
| d | perimeter: distant | 4 | heat pump |
| S1 | thermally conditioned space | 5 | district heating/cooling |
| S2 | space outside thermal envelope | 6 | substation (low/medium voltage and possible storage) |

Figure 3-2: Building level: assessment boundaries (source: EN ISO 52000)

3.1.2. Energy flows & Sankey diagrams

The logic behind the calculations of the energy KPI is based on comparing ‘the energy needed’ (energy need or demand) to ‘the energy required to deliver the needed energy’ (the delivered energy). Not all of the energy flows that happen naturally are considered in a direct way. The energy losses for example, are not taken into account, but they are reflected indirectly by the energy-efficiency indicators. For example, the energy demand for space heating is the heat that flows into the building through the emission systems and that is required to maintain thermal comfort. The delivered energy is delivered by different systems in which energy is injected into the systems’ processes. In the case of a GEOTABS circuit, the delivered energy is the electric energy used by the compressor and the circulation pumps of the borefield and heat distribution systems in the building. There is a part of the delivered energy that comes from the ground, but through a natural thermodynamic process that happens in the heat pump. That energy is not accounted for because it is not a real cost for the system.

A simple scheme of a thermodynamic process for heating (and the version for cooling in a small figure) can be seen in the Figure 3-3. The INPUT A represents the costly energy (work) and the OUTPUT A represents the heat that effectively is used for heating (the energy need/demand). In case of cooling, the scheme is the same, but the interest is the INPUT B, that represents the heat extracted, while the OUTPUT A remains secondary.

In reality, it is difficult to measure the heat that is effectively released by the surface of a radiator or the surfaces of the TABS by convection or radiation (= the net energy need/demand), but the heat that passes from the production system into the distribution system (= the gross energy demand) or from the distribution system into the emission system, can be measured instead (and similarly for the cooling). Especially for the TABS with its high thermal inertia, there is a non-negligible difference between the heat that the distribution system puts into the TABS, and the heat emitted by the surface. Nevertheless, to have realistic and consistent scenarios between the simulations and the reality, every model considers the emission systems as part of the thermal zones. In other words, the heat that is delivered to the emission system is the heat delivered to the thermal zones. Of course still, in the simulation models the TABS behaviour is modelled and contributes to the thermal comfort in the zones.

Figure 3-3: Basic scheme of heating and cooling processes. Note the similarities.

In this report, the energy flows in the systems are presented using simplified Sankey diagrams, as illustrated in Figure 3-4. They show the main energy flows at the building level composed by flows between some nodes that represent relevant components. This kind of diagrams can help the reader to understand the flows through the system. Nevertheless, they do not contain all the details of the actual energy flows. Some components have been merged into others (components level) respecting the energy flows at a system level and at building level. For example, the circulation pumps for the TABS are not represented separately in the diagram, but the simulated electric energy used for moving them is added to the TABS system which is represented on the diagram. The diagram tries to be as simple as possible but to show correct flows at system and building levels.

On the diagrams, the energy always flows from left to right, including the heat extracted from the building. So, the energy sources are located on the left side of the diagram, while the heat sinks are located on the right side. The main functions of the building systems that are considered in the virtual test-bed (heating, cooling, ventilation) are located in the centre of the diagram. All the shown values are in kWh/m²/year. The functions determine the colours of the nodes and energy flows:

- Red (Crimson): elements involved in heating.
- Blue: Elements involved in cooling.
- Yellow: Electricity.
- Green: Ventilation function and heat recovery.
- Grey: Primary energy.

Furthermore, the flows that represent the heating and cooling demands are represented with darker colours on the Sankey diagrams (intense red/orange for heating demand and intense blue for cooling demand).

All Sankey diagrams were generated with the webtool developed by Dénes Csala [5] and graphically edited to include some extra information.

Figure 3-4: Example of a Sankey diagram (from Sankey Diagram Generator by Dénes Csala)

The energy flows shown on the Sankey diagrams are summarised in a summary table, such as Table 3-1, that give an overview of the most relevant energy parameters. They, in this, complement the Sankey diagrams.

From the point of view of space heating and cooling, the main flows can be divided and grouped in heat injected in the building and heat extracted from the building. Three main categories were defined to divide each of the heat flows. In the case of heat that is delivered to the building, the first one is the active injected heat, which corresponds to the heat produced by the different heat generators such as HPs or boilers that goes directly into the conditioned zones through different emitters. The second category is the pre-heating of the ventilation air, which corresponds to the heat that is produced by the heat generators to pre-heat the outdoor air before it is injected into the conditioned zones and typically after heat recovery has taken place. This process occurs for the whole building and the final temperature of the air after the pre-heating may not be enough to satisfy the thermal comfort in the conditioned zones. The last category is the heat recovery of the ventilation, in which heat is recovered from the extracted ventilation air and transferred to the supply air. In this process no heat generators are involved. Equivalent categories are defined for the heat extracted from the building (cooling). Within these categories, the energy is split into the energy related to the GEOTABS part of the system, and the nonGEOTABS part of the system. In the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenarios (see Figure 2-3), the GEOTABS part of the system represents the primary GEOTABS system, with TABS, GSHP and GSHX as main components. The secondary system, consisting of a fast-reacting emission system and a secondary production system, is included in the nonGEOTABS part of the system. In the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (see Figure 2-2), the latter nonGEOTABS part is the only system involved. All heat flows and categories have an associated electricity or gas use, which is the basis for estimating the primary energy use. The parameter "Net space heat" (Table xx) provides insight into the net demand of the building: a heating-dominated building will show a positive

value for this parameter, while a cooling-dominated building will have a negative value. The variation of this value among the different scenarios in the same building can indirectly reflect the variation in ventilation rates, since the internal gains, occupation profiles and weather do not vary along the scenarios.

Table 3-1: Summary table – Parameters descriptions

Parameter	Group	Description
Active injected heat (local space heating)		<i>Heat that flows to the conditioned spaces, measured from the emitters. Recovery is not included.</i>
	GEOTABS	<i>Heat flow that goes from GSHP → (TABS/Floor heating) → zone</i>
	Electricity	<i>Associated electricity to the process</i>
	nonGEOTABS	<i>The rest of active injected heat. In general: (Boiler/GSHP) → not(TABS/Floor heating) → zone</i>
	Electricity	<i>Associated electricity to the process</i>
	Natural gas	<i>Associated natural gas to the process</i>
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating)		<i>Heat flow that goes from (Boiler/GSHP) → AHU</i>
	Electricity	<i>Associated electricity to the process</i>
	Natural gas	<i>Associated natural gas to the process</i>
Recovery heat from ventilation		<i>Heat recovered from the exhaust air that goes again to the zone</i>
Active extracted heat (local space cooling)		<i>Heat that flows from the conditioned spaces, measured from the heat receivers. Recovery is not included</i>
	GEOTABS	<i>Heat flow that goes from zone → (TABS/Floor heating) → (GSHP/ground heat exchanger)</i>
	Electricity	<i>Associated electricity to the process</i>
	nonGEOTABS	<i>from zone → (any heat receiver) → not(GSHP/ground heat exchanger)</i>
	Electricity	<i>Associated electricity to the process</i>
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling)		<i>Heat flow that goes from AHU → (any heat sink)</i>
	Electricity	<i>Associated electricity to the process</i>
Recovery heat from ventilation		<i>Excess of heat absorbed by the exhaust air from the incoming airflow</i>
Recirculated heat (simultaneous heating and cooling)		<i>Heat transferred between zones by TABS due to the different temperatures in the zones. Warm zone → TABS → cold zone.</i>
Net space heat ([space heating] - [space cooling])		<i>([heating]) - [Active extracted heat] - [Pre-cooling ventilation] - [Recovery (cooling)]</i>
Ventilation (electricity fans)		<i>Electricity associated to the fans</i>
Total electricity		<i>Sum of all electricity fields in the table</i>
Total natural gas		<i>Sum of all natural gas fields in the table</i>
Primary energy (electricity: $\times 2$; gas: $\times 1.1$)		<i>(Total electricity) \times (electricity conversion factor) + (Total natural gas) \times (natural gas conversion factor)</i>

3.1.3. Efficiencies

From the summary Table 3-1 it is possible to define efficiencies for relevant groups. Each efficiency is the result of dividing the heat injected/extracted to/from the building of each group by the costly energy provided to the system (indicated by the groups named electricity and/or natural gas). For some processes, the efficiency is equivalent to the seasonal coefficient of performance (SCOP), while for others is just a way to represent how costly a process is when transforming the energy into heat. Table 3-2 shows the entries of the efficiencies. The last three rows summarize the overall system efficiencies for space heating, space cooling and the combination of both.

Table 3-2: Table of efficiencies and GEOTABS share

Parameter	Group	Description
Active injected heat (local space heating) (efficiency)		$(Heat\ GEOTABS + Heat\ nonGOETABS) / (Electricity + Natural\ gas)$
	GEOTABS (SCOP system)	$(Heat\ GEOTABS) / (Electricity\ GEOTABS)$
	nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	$(Heat\ nonGEOTABS) / (Electricity\ nonGEOTABS + Natural\ gas\ nonGEOTABS)$
	Share GEOTABS [-]	$(Heat\ GEOTABS) / (Heat\ GEOTABS + Heat\ nonGOETABS)$
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) (efficiency)		$(Heat\ pre-heating) / (Electricity\ pre-heating + Natural\ gas\ pre-heating)$
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) (efficiency)		$(Heat\ GEOTABS + Heat\ nonGOETABS) / (Electricity\ GEOTABS + Electricity\ nonGEOTABS)$
	GEOTABS (SCOP system)	$(Heat\ GEOTABS) / (Electricity\ GEOTABS)$
	nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	$(Heat\ nonGEOTABS) / (Electricity\ nonGEOTABS)$
	Share GEOTABS [-]	$(Heat\ GEOTABS) / (Heat\ GEOTABS + Heat\ nonGOETABS)$
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) (efficiency)		$(Heat\ pre-cooling) / (Electricity\ pre-cooling)$
Global efficiency heating + pre-heating		$(Heat\ GEOTABS + Heat\ nonGOETABS + Heat\ pre-heating) / (electricity + gas, heating + pre-heating)$
Global share GEOTABS heating + pre-heating		$(Heat\ GEOTABS) / (Heat\ GEOTABS + Heat\ nonGOETABS + Heat\ pre-heating)$
GSHP SCOP space heating (component)		$(Heat\ delivered\ by\ the\ GSHP) / (Electricity\ used\ for\ heating)$
Global efficiency cooling + pre-cooling		$(Heat\ GEOTABS\ (cool) + Heat\ nonGOETABS\ (cool) + Heat\ pre-cooling) / (electricity\ cooling + pre-cooling)$
Global share GEOTABS cooling + pre-cooling		$(Heat\ GEOTABS\ (cool)) / (Heat\ GEOTABS\ (cool) + Heat\ nonGOETABS\ (cool) + Heat\ pre-cooling)$
GSHP SCOP cooling (component)		$(Heat\ extracted\ by\ the\ GSHP) / (Electricity\ used\ for\ cooling)$
Global efficiency space heating and cooling		$(All\ injected\ heat + All\ extracted\ heat) / (Total\ electricity\ and\ natural\ gas\ for\ space\ heating\ and\ space\ cooling)$

3.1.4. Share of renewable energy and geothermal balance

When estimating the performance of hybridGEOTABS, the share of renewable energy sources at the building level, and more specifically the share of geothermal energy at system level, are important indicators. The performance indicators therefore include the share of the renewable sources at the systems and building levels. Also, at building level indicators show which part of the renewable sources comes from the ground source heat pumps (GSHP). At the systems level, the indicators focus on the GEOTABS share for the different functions. Every share is calculated based on the delivered energy to the element of interest. For example, for heating (cooling), the renewable share will be calculated by looking at the delivered (extracted) energy to (from) the zones of the building. That energy will come (leave) from (to) different sources.

3.1.5. Primary energy and CO₂-emissions

At the building level, the primary energy and CO₂-emissions are estimated using conversion factors. The primary energy factor is a measure for the amount of primary energy that is required to deliver 1 kWh of energy to the building following the assessment boundary as depicted in Figure 3-2, thus accounting for the conversion and transformation losses outside the assessment boundary. The total primary energy factor, consists of a non-renewable and a renewable part. Especially for electricity, it differs between countries, depending on the mix of electricity sources used. In this study, we use the total primary energy factors as they are more representative for the overall energy-efficiency. The factors used are displayed in Table 3-3 (the non-renewable factors are informative but not used) and are based on the work of Hamels et al. (2020) [6]. For each case-study building, the primary energy is estimated using the average European factor, as well as the country-specific factor, for the electricity mix estimates of the year 2020.

The CO₂-emissions are used as indicator for the environmental impact of the system. The focus is on the impacts related to the energy use in the operation of the building (for heating, cooling and ventilation), not on the environmental impact related to the embodied materials. Therefore, the CO₂-emissions are the main greenhouse gas emissions occurring and are a good indicator for the global warming potential. The CO₂-emission factors for electricity are also based on the work of Hamels et al. (2020) [6].

Table 3-3: Primary energy and CO₂-emission factors

Electricity	CO₂	PE total	PE non-renewable
EU2020	0.26	2	1.6
Belgium	0.059	2.4	2.1
Switzerland	0.036	1.7	1.1
Czech Republic	0.537	2.4	2.3
Natural Gas	CO₂	PE	PE non-renewable
EN ISO 52000-1:2017	0.22	1.1	1.1

3.1.6. Energy signature

The building energy parameters can be plotted against the equivalent outdoor temperature (T_{eq}), which is defined as:

$$T_{eq} = 0.6 \cdot \theta_{ed-0} + 0.3 \cdot \theta_{ed-1} + 0.1 \cdot \theta_{ed-2}$$

Where T_{eq} is the equivalent temperature of the present day in °C and every term θ_{ed-i} is the mean outdoor temperature in °C of the i -day before the present day, $i \in \{1,2,3\}$.

Expressing the energy use against T_{eq} gives the possibility to compare different scenarios of the same building under different weather conditions by using tools like regression analysis to make a proper comparison. This makes sense in real buildings, but as the simulations use the same weather conditions, the energy signature graph becomes a secondary plot. In this deliverable, the energy signatures are shown as informative graphs equivalent to the corresponding ones from the monitoring of the buildings in the [D4.12](#). Here, the analysis is made directly on the measured data instead of the information given by this kind of graphs, since all data is available and no further statistical operations are needed to make a fair comparison between scenarios.

3.1.7. Other considerations: units, time and normalisation

Working/non-working hours and days

For the offices building and the school we can clearly distinguish between times that the building is in use and times that it is not used. The first type, indicated along the document as “working hours”, are all the hours when the building is in use and the comfort limits are active (students at class and office workers at the office). The non-working hours are the rest of the days (typically nights, weekends and holidays) when the buildings are not in normal use and the thermal comfort limits have a setback.

The working days are all the days where there is at least one working hour. The rest of the days are called “non-working days”. The simulations reproduce the same share of working and non-working hours and days in all scenarios, so in this deliverable it is not necessary to make this distinction to make a proper energy analysis. Nevertheless, the energy signature figures do differentiate between working and non-working days to be congruent with the figures shown in [D4.12](#).

Normalisation to size

The results are given by square meter of the net conditioned area, since that gives the reader a better idea of the energy use and it can be used to compare with other buildings with different sizes. As a result, energy use is typically expressed in kWh/m²/year.

Time transformed to natural months

All time-series refer to month and day, for easier understanding. As the weather files represent a standard year, there is not any specific natural year to refer the results to. The results of the simulations do not start on the same moment. Haus M and Infrac start on 1st January and Ter Potterie on 10th January (according to the weather file). Furthermore, the 10 first days of all results have been removed in any calculation, figure or table shown in this document.

3.2. Cost performance indicators

3.2.1. Methodology and assumptions

The calculation of the costs is primarily based on the EC Regulation No. 244/2012 for ex. In order to provide a consistent report for all the considered buildings, the templates and required data types were discussed among the partners that regularly work with cost estimates (Boydens, Lemon Consult and Energoklastr). First, a common data table was negotiated, and then it was checked against 244/2012 for compliance.

The European Commission (EC) also issued a Guide to Cost Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects², which proposes a general schematic for cost benefit analysis (CBA), and the EC Regulation No. 244/2012 can be used as one part of the wider CBA.

Figure 3-5: CBA structure according to Sartori et al. [8] The cost performance indicators represent the highlighted part

The directive requires the following cost categories to be evaluated:

- Initial investment costs;
- Running costs – these include costs for periodic replacement of building elements and might include, if appropriate, the earnings from energy produced;
- Energy costs – reflect overall energy cost including energy price, capacity tariffs and grid tariffs;
- Disposal costs if appropriate.

² Sartori, Davide et al. *Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis*. Brussels: EC, DG Regio, 2015. ISBN 978-92-79-34796-2

- Cost of greenhouse gas emissions. These reflect the quantified, monetised and discounted operational costs of CO₂ resulting from the greenhouse gas emissions in tonnes of CO₂ equivalent over the calculation period.

In practice, the initial investment costs are usually called CapEx, and the rest of the costs are called OpEx. In our analyses, we will follow this usual division into CapEx and OpEx, with a finer categorisation according to the Directive.

3.2.2. Scope

As already explained, the scenarios proposed in the project aim at comparing various combinations of TABS, secondary system and MPC. As the other parts of the building (foundations, envelope, but also major part of the project and design) are common, they will not be evaluated. Only the differences between the scenarios will be evaluated.

The analysis of the cost performance indicators within this deliverable is also consistent with the results of the Cost Benefit Analysis of Work Package 5 (D5.5).

3.2.3. Investment horizon

The directive requires that the investment horizon is at least 20 years for administration buildings and 30 years for residential buildings. We will therefore consider the investment horizon of 30 years for all the case studies, in order to have consistent and comparable results.

Note that the investment horizon is not defined for schools (the case of Líbeznice), as for many governments there is no reason to calculate ROI for state funded schools. The long-term cost indicators for the school building are thus academic and will be calculated for comparison purposes only.

3.2.4. Discount rates

The discount rates have to be defined for Belgium, Czech Republic, Switzerland and EU27. Due to the nature of long-term investments, average values over the last couple of years cannot be used, as all considered markets have steadily falling discount rates (e.g., in Belgium, from more than 8 % in 1990s to virtual 0 % now). Following discount rates have been estimated for the 30 years investment horizon, based on indicative values suggested by the European Central Bank:

Table 3-4: Discount rates

Region	Discount Rate
Belgium	1,5 %
Switzerland	1,0 %
Czech Republic	2,5 %
EU27	2,0 %

3.2.5. Earning from produced energy

In our calculations, we will not consider the earnings from the energy produced within the buildings, as the MPC is tuned in such a way that all the energy produced by local sources is consumed within the building. The reason for this tuning is that we assume the market price for the energy supplied from the grid will always be higher than the buy-out energy price, thus consuming the energy inhouse is economically more viable.

3.2.6. Disposal costs

Furthermore, we will not consider the disposal costs, as the differences between the observed scenarios will be insignificant – most of the disposal costs apply to the disposal of structural elements, which is the same for all the scenarios.

3.2.7. CO₂-emission costs

The CO₂-emission costs are calculated according to the EU Emission Trading System, which will enter into its Phase IV in 2021. The future prices of emissions are very difficult to estimate. The experience from the first three phases tells us that the market price for CO₂-emissions was much lower than expected, i.e. the costs for reducing the CO₂-emissions are in general lower than originally anticipated.

The costs of CO₂-emissions skyrocketed in 2018, after the presentation of the “Winter package”, from around 5 EUR/ton to the current 25 EUR/ton, as the market reflected the much more ambitious goals for the climate change mitigation. However, the publication of the European Green Deal in December 2019 seems to have little to no effect on the CO₂-emission prices. It may well be that the market is already on the level where the costs for the CO₂ reduction are settled.

For the reasons mentioned above, we will take the initial price of the CO₂-emissions at 25 EUR/ton, and we will use the EU27 discount rate.

Figure 3-6: CO₂-emission prices (EUR/ton), 2010-2020

3.2.8. Investment costs

As already mentioned, only investments relevant for the comparison study will be considered. These include:

- Components of the primary production system
- Components of the secondary production system (if installed)
- Primary emission system
- Secondary emission system

- Control system
- Collaterals – devices not directly connected to above systems, but necessary for their function

A detailed list of components is provided in [D5.5](#).

3.2.9. Running costs

We consider the life-span of the building construction to be 30 years, i.e. no substantial construction component will need replacement. However, detailed maintenance costs have to be estimated, as maintenance is a significant part of total running costs. Some of the technologies will be replaced as follows during the 30 year period:

- Batteries: after 10 and 20 years
- Heat pump, gas boiler or other secondary system, chillers, control system (including MPC): after 15 years
- Photovoltaics: no replacement within 30 years

3.2.10. Energy costs

We will use the same structure of energy costs as described in part 3.1.3.

3.2.11. Sensitivity analysis

The overall result of the cost performance is strongly dependent on various factors, mainly energy prices, discount rates, CO₂-emission prices, etc. Sensitivity analysis enables the identification of the 'critical' variables of the project. Such variables are those whose variations, be they positive or negative, have the largest impact on the project's financial and/or economic performance. The analysis is carried out by varying one variable at a time and determining the effect of that change on the Net Present Value (NPV). As a guiding criterion, the general recommendation is to consider 'critical' those variables for which a variation of $\pm 1\%$ of the value adopted in the base case gives rise to a variation of more than 1% in the value of the NPV. The tested variables should be deterministically independent and as disaggregated as possible. Correlated variables would give rise to distortions in the results and double-counting.

3.2.12. Final cost performance overview

For the final cost performance overview, we will use the structure recommended by EC Regulation No. 244/2012:

Table 3-5: Structure of the cost performance

Variant	Initial investment cost (referred to starting year)	Annual running cost			Calculation period	Cost of greenhouse gas emissions	Residual value	Discount rate	Estimated economic lifetime	Disposal cost	Global cost calculated (NPV)
		Annual maintenance cost	Operational cost	Energy cost by fuel with the medium energy price scenario							

4. Analysis: Haus M multi-family building

4.1. Building and scenarios

4.1.1. Haus M

Figure 4-1: Haus M – Pictures (Photography courtesy of Johannes Marburg (left) and Ursula Meisser (right))

Haus M is a 5360 m² residential apartment building in Zürich, Switzerland. It consists of 29 apartments over five floors centred around a large unconditioned atrium with staircase, a 950 m² day care centre (kindergarten) on the ground floor and a basement. The building is south-oriented and has shading systems that are manually controlled. It is a heavy-weight building and has a high insulation level with U-values lower than 0.15 W/m²/K for the opaque elements and under 1.1 W/m²/K for the glazing. The building is ventilated with a natural supply (via openings above windows) and mechanical exhaust ventilation system. One heat pump recovers the heat from the extract air and uses it to heat the domestic hot water. Additionally, solar collectors also provide heat for domestic hot water. A second, bigger heat pump is connected to the GSHX (consisting of horizontal collectors) and delivers heating to the floor heating system (pipe depth 5 cm). The building is not equipped with a cooling system. Figure 4-2 is a schematic representation of the systems in the actual building.

Figure 4-2: Haus M – Energy systems schematic

In the virtual test-bed, several scenarios of Haus M were developed (see Figure 4-3). The as built scenario *hybridGEOTABS_AB* mostly represents the real building, although focusing on the HVAC-systems that are essential in the hybridGEOTABS project. Then, starting from the as-built model, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenarios are developed, as explained in section 2.1. Since in the context of this project, Haus M is a case-study building but not a demonstration building, no *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario is available.

Figure 4-3: Haus M – Scenarios scheme

4.1.2. As-Built scenario: *hybridGEOTABS_AB*

The as-built scenario model is the most similar to the real Haus M building. It was validated using the measurement data of the building (and for that purpose also used real weather data from the same period) and was explained in detail in deliverable [D4.7](#). In summary, for modelling the building, rooms that are similar in terms of function, building physics and orientation, are clustered into zones according to the scheme in Figure 4-4. The building envelope and structure are modelled according to the properties of the actual building. A basic shading schedule emulating manual shading use was implemented as well.

Table 4-1: Haus M – Similarities and differences of the different scenarios

Haus M	hybridGEOTABS_AB	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	nonGEOTABS-RBC
Envelope	Haus M		
Occupancy	Occupancy profile		
Weather	Zurich (Measured data)	TMY Zurich (Meteonorm)	
Ventilation	Mechanical extraction fixed flow rate	Mechanical extraction fixed flow rate + CO ₂ control [900 ppm max]	
Primary heating system	Floor heating + GSHP		FCU + Natural Gas Boiler
Secondary heating system	ASHP from DHW production	FCU + Natural Gas Boiler	NO
Heat recovery (heating)	NO	YES	
Primary cooling system	NO	Floor cooling + GSHP (the same components as hybridGEOTABS_AB)	FCU + Chiller
Secondary cooling system	NO	FCU + Chiller	NO
Heat recovery (cooling)	NO	YES	
DHW production	ASHP (it extracts heat from the ventilation system)	NO	

In both scenarios, the controls are based on the outdoor temperature. This parameter of the weather file used in the simulations is shown with its corresponding RMOT in Figure 4-5.

Figure 4-5: Haus M – Outdoor temperature and RMOT

4.2. Building behaviour

For a correct interpretation of the performance results, it is necessary to observe the indoor temperatures in the different scenarios. Figure 4-6 shows the Haus M temperature profiles for the two simulated scenarios.

The plotted temperatures in the violin plots are the hourly indoor operative temperatures of all conditioned zones in the building (13 zones in the model) during one year. The operative temperatures in Figure 4-6 are plotted in function of the RMOT, which also defines the comfort regions included as coloured bands in the background of the plot. To complete the graph, the frequencies of the RMOT are plotted to express the occurrence of the RMOT throughout the year.

Haus M: Operative Temperature vs RMOT - 113880 points by scenario
Conditioned Zones: 13 | Working hours: 8760 (100 % of 8760 hours of the standard year)

Figure 4-6: Haus M – Operative temperature vs RMOT

When comparing the two baseline scenarios *nonGEOTABS-RBC* and *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* in Figure 4-6, the indoor temperature ranges are found to be nicely within the comfort bounds for most of the time of the year. Looking more in detail, remark that the indoor operative temperatures in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline typically show a slightly higher spread for the same RMOT when compared to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. This can be explained by two differences in both scenarios. On one hand, the different combinations of HVAC-system components and controls lead to different thermal inertias for both baselines. The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* has a HVAC-system with rather low thermal inertia. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* also has a fast-reacting secondary system, but the primary GEOTABS system with its higher thermal inertia results in slower reaction of the indoor environment and thus higher variations along the day (Figure 4-7). On the other hand, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* allows to have heating and cooling at the same time in different building zones, leading to a better response of the temperatures in individual zones. In the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* the entire building is either in heating, neutral or cooling mode at each moment for the GEOTABS system. The secondary system is able to heat (cool) when the primary system is in cooling mode (heating mode), but to avoid the undesirable situation of simultaneous heating and cooling in a zone, the control forces the secondary system to be activated with relaxed setpoint temperatures. For heating, the setpoint is 0.5 °C higher in the secondary system, while for cooling the setpoint is 0.5 °C lower than the setpoint in the GEOTABS system.

To complement the previous graph, the operative temperatures are shown as time series in Figure 4-7. On the graph it is noticeable that the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* has a good accuracy in reaching the set temperature to achieve the thermal comfort, especially in heating season. Nevertheless, the temperatures have smoother profiles on the *nonGEOTABS*, which is a reflection of the different characteristics of both scenarios explained in the previous paragraph.

Figure 4-7: Haus M – Operative temperatures in dwellings and KiTa (coloured in red) and comfort bands for all scenarios

The reason to not have a similar accuracy in the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario is a matter of the control based on the temperature of the air instead of the operative temperatures. Figure 4-8 shows that the control in *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has also good accuracy for the air temperatures in the dwellings. Nevertheless, the KiTa shows certain periods where the temperature experiences a drop (in January and in December). This behaviour can be seen on the operative temperatures as well.

Figure 4-8: Haus M – Air temperatures in dwellings and KiTa (coloured in red) in *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario

Regarding the CO₂-concentration, both scenarios show a maximum concentration of 950 ppm in any conditioned zone. The CO₂-concentration is periodic, following a similar behaviour as the occupation profiles in both scenarios. Figure 4-9 shows a 31-days window of the CO₂-concentration. For both scenarios the values are practically the same, since they have the same ventilation system, building envelope, weather conditions and occupancy profiles.

Figure 4-9: Haus M – CO₂-concentration in [ppm]

4.3. Energy performance

4.3.1. Energy flows

Simplified Sankey diagrams visualising the energy flows along the simulated year (see section 3.1.2) are shown in Figure 4-10 for the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario and Figure 4-11 for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario respectively. The energy demand of the building is represented as intense-coloured flows on the graphs.

PE factor natural gas: **1.1** (kWh PE)/kWh
 PE factor electricity: **2** (kWh PE)/kWh

Primary energy (costly)
Electricity
Space heating
Heating demand (space heating)
Space heating
Cooling demand (space cooling)
Ventilation
Heat recovery/recirculation

Haus M
nonGEOTABS-RBC scenario
 Main energy flows in the building (normalized by conditioned area)
 Values in [kWh/m²/year]

Figure 4-10: Haus M – Sankey diagram for the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario

PE factor natural gas: **1.1** (kWh PE)/kWh
 PE factor electricity: **2** (kWh PE)/kWh

Primary energy (costly)
Electricity
Space heating
Heating demand (space heating)
Space heating
Cooling demand (space cooling)
Ventilation
Heat recovery/recirculation

Haus M
hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario
 Main energy flows in the building (normalized by conditioned area)
 Values in [kWh/m²/year]

Figure 4-11: Haus M – Sankey diagram for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario

Table 4-2 is directly made from the Sankey diagrams (Figure 4-10 and Figure 4-11). It shows a summary of the described energy flows for both scenarios obtained from the simulations. The table and the diagrams include the primary energy use based on the global factors exposed in Table 3-3. Table 4-3 shows the efficiencies calculated from the values in the previous table.

Table 4-2: Haus M – Summary table extracted from the energy flows

Haus M - units in [kWh/m ² /year]	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC
Active injected heat (local space heating) - thermal energy	49.9	39.5
GEOTABS - thermal energy	0.0	37.5
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	12.0
nonGEOTABS - thermal energy	49.9	2.0
Electricity - electric energy	1.2	0.3
Natural gas - thermal energy	55.5	2.2
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) - thermal energy	0.0	0.0
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	0.0
Natural gas - thermal energy	0.0	0.0
Recovery heat from ventilation - thermal energy	24.4	23.7
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) - thermal energy	25.3	13.3
GEOTABS - thermal energy	0.0	5.9
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	3.8
nonGEOTABS - thermal energy	25.3	7.4
Electricity - electric energy	5.5	1.7
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) - thermal energy	0.0	0.0
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	0.0
Recovery heat from ventilation - thermal energy	0.3	0.3
Recirculated heat (simultaneous heating and cooling) - thermal energy	0.0	0.0
Net space heat ([space heating] - [space cooling]) - thermal energy	24.7	26.1
Ventilation (electricity fans) - electric energy	1.0	1.0
Total electricity - electric energy	7.7	18.7
Total natural gas - thermal energy	55.5	2.2
Primary energy (electricity: x2; gas: x1.1)	76.4	39.9

Table 4-3: Haus M – Efficiencies and GEOTABS share

Haus M - Efficiencies and GEOTABS share. Dimensionless	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC
Active injected heat (local space heating) (efficiency)	0.88	2.74
GEOTABS (SCOP system)		3.13
nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	0.88	0.81
Share GEOTABS	0%	95%
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) (efficiency)		
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) (efficiency)	4.62	2.42
GEOTABS (SCOP system)		1.57
nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	4.62	4.25
Share GEOTABS	0%	45%
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) (efficiency)		
Global efficiency heating+pre-heating	0.88	2.74
Global share GEOTABS heating + pre-heating		95%
GSHP SCOP space heating (component)		3.23
Global efficiency cooling+pre-cooling	4.62	2.42
Global share GEOTABS cooling + pre-cooling		45%
GSHP SCOP cooling (component)		2.04
Global efficiency space heating and cooling	1.21	2.65

Figure 4-12 represents for the two scenarios the yearly heat exchanged with the conditioned zones via active heating and cooling, via pre-heating of the ventilation air (not applicable in this case) and via heat recovery in the ventilation system. It is remarkable that the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario exchanges less energy with the conditioned zones than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. In heating mode, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* injects 20.8 % less heat in the building than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (39.5 kWh/m²/year vs. 49.9 kWh/m²/year). It also extracts 47.4 % less heat than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (13.3 kWh/m²/year vs. 25.3 kWh/m²/year). This can be explained by the different controls in both scenarios. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has a slower and more complex control that limits the changes between heating and cooling modes, while the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario can react instantaneously if required. The faster control leads to less temperature gradients along the day, but also an increased energy demand, while the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* presents more fluctuations in the temperatures, but all located within the thermal comfort band. In the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, about 95 % of the heating demand is provided by the GEOTABS system. Therefore, in the real-life implementation a secondary heating system is not required and the building can rely fully on GEOTABS for heating purposes. The cooling demand is rather limited and provided for 44 % by the GEOTABS system. In the real-life building no cooling system is applied, and some overheating in the summer is accepted (see D4.7).

Figure 4-12: Haus M – Heat delivered/extracted to/from the building (per sub-system)

Taking into account the gross (or costly) energy needed to provide the heating and cooling to the building zones, Table 4-3 shows the system efficiencies. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has a better efficiency than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* in heating (2.74 and 0.88, respectively), where the SCOP of the GEOTABS is about 3.1. The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has a much better efficiency during cooling (4.62 vs. 2.42), as a result of the low efficiency of the GEOTABS in cooling in these simulations. Remark that the heat pump is modelled based on the original heat pump in the building, while today GSHP's with much higher performances in both heating and cooling are on the market. The heat pump has a COP of 2.5 in cooling, while for the chiller a COP of 5 was used.

Moreover, the simulations only accounted for active cooling, and not for the (more energy-efficient) passive cooling. Also for heating, this heat pump has quite a low COP of 3.5. In case a GSHP with a higher SCOP of 7 would be used in the hybridGEOTABS scenario and passive cooling for GEOTABS cooling, the efficiency of heating would rise to around 5.7 for the GEOTABS heating (4.3 for the whole heating function) and 7.9 for GEOTABS cooling (4.9 for the whole cooling function).

4.3.2. Primary energy use

Figure 4-13: Haus M – Primary energy (per sub-system) using EU factors

Figure 4-14: Haus M – Primary energy (per sub-system) using local factors

Figure 4-13 and Figure 4-14 show the total primary energy use for heating, cooling and ventilation of the building, per sub-category. The first figure uses the primary energy factors for the EU while the second one used the local

factors for Switzerland, where the electricity mix is more energy-efficient than the EU average (see section 3.1.5). The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* leads to primary energy reductions of 47.8 % and 53.8 % for the two PEF's respectively. Comparing the change in PEF's for both scenarios, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario benefits more from the transition to a cleaner electricity mix, both in absolute and relative terms (-3 % vs. -15 %).

The greatest share of the total primary energy comes from the heating in both cases, but it is more acute in the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, as a result of the much lower efficiency of the gas boiler as compared to the GSHP. Regarding the space cooling, its use is smaller in the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. This can be explained looking at the COP of the chiller, which is greater than the COP of the GSHP in the model. In both scenarios the chiller is identical (used as secondary system in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario) but, as was explained above, the SCOP of the heat pump in cooling mode is lower (2.5) and no passive cooling is used.

Figure 4-15 shows the scatter plot of the primary energy use (with the average EU factor) against the equivalent outdoor temperature and provides some insight in the efficiency throughout the seasons. In general, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario uses more energy than the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. On the left side (heating mode) of the figure, where $T_{eq} < 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the differences are more evident, as a result of GEOTABS efficiency and the lower heat demand in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. On the right side (cooling mode) the differences are smaller, despite the higher efficiency of *nonGEOTABS-RBC* in cooling mode, because of a higher cooling demand in that scenario. The centre of the graph (not heating nor cooling dominant), where T_{eq} is around $12\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the trendline indicates that the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario uses more energy, because of its stricter control, which leads to increased heating and cooling demand, in all parts of the graph.

Figure 4-15: Haus M – Energy signature (primary energy with EU factors)

Finally, the ground balance for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario in the simulated year is shown in Table 4-4. The building extracts 1.86 times more heat from the ground than it injects, leading to a significant imbalance in the ground.

Table 4-4: Haus M – Ground balance

Haus M - Ground balance	hybridGEOTABS-RBC
Heat extracted from the ground [kWh/m²/year]	26.22
Heat delivered to the ground [kWh/m²/year]	9.18
Ground balance ((heat extracted)-[heat delivered]) [kWh/m²/year]	17.05
Ground balance ratio ((heat extracted)/[heat delivered]) [-]	2.86

4.4. Environmental performance

Figure 4-16 and Figure 4-17 show the total CO₂-emissions from natural gas used and the electricity from the grid used by the heating, cooling and ventilation systems to operate, using the factors documented in 3.1.5.

The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline produces 5.35 (kg CO₂)/m²/year, which is about 62.3 % lower than the emissions of the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (14.21 (kg CO₂)/m²/year), using the average EU factors. Using the local factors for Switzerland, which has a low-carbon electricity mix, the difference is much higher, where the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario emits only about 1.15 (kg CO₂)/m²/year, which is 90.8 % less CO₂ than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (12.48 (kg CO₂)/m²/year).

Figure 4-16: Haus M – CO₂-emissions (EU factor)

Figure 4-17: Haus M – CO₂-emissions (local factor)

4.5. Cost performance

For the cost performance of Haus M and for the two variants, we have assumed the following additional inputs, listed in Table 4-5.

Table 4-5: Haus M – Cost categories.

Input	hGT-RBC	nonGT-RBC
Basic construction costs	16 071 00 CHF	16 071 00 CHF
Extra technologies (incl. chillers)	868 136 CHF	740 948 CHF
Design fees	170 674 CHF	112 353 CHF
Gas boiler	–	61 572 CHF
Heat pump	307 858 CHF	0 CHF
Borefield cost	246 286 CHF	0 CHF
Electricity price	0.16 CHF/kWh	0.16 CHF/kWh
Discount rate	1 %	1 %
CO₂ price	54 CHF/ton	54 CHF/ton

We have also assumed the local energy conversion ratios. The prices are all indicated in Swiss Francs, as conversion to EUR would not be illustrative, due to different discount factors.

Based on the EC Regulation No. 244/2012, we performed the cost benefit analysis with the following results:

Table 4-6: Haus M – Global cost calculated (Net Present Value)

Variant		hGT-RBC	nonGT-RBC
Initial investment cost		17 109 810 CHF	16 924 301 CHF
Annual running cost	Maintenance cost	13 902 CHF	10 426 CHF
	Operational cost (reinvestments)	152 396 CHF	128 835 CHF
	Energy cost by fuel with the medium energy price scenario	15 026 CHF	32 461 CHF
Calculation period		30	30
Cost of greenhouse gas emissions		8 671 CHF	94 102 CHF
Residual value		3 010 669 CHF	3 010 669 CHF
Discount rate		1,00%	1,00%
Estimated economic lifetime		30	30
Disposal cost		N/A	N/A
Global cost calculated (NPV)		20 586 317 CHF	20 012 689 CHF

It is clear that the hybridGEOTABS with RBC has a bigger life cycle cost (LCC) than the nonGEOTABS variant, however, the difference is not significant, only 573 628 CHF, which is less than 3 % of the life cycle cost. For various scenarios, such as with energy price doubling in 30 years, the lifecycle costs become equal (for details, see D5.5).

It is also interesting to look at the cumulative costs of the basic scenario – this is shown in Figure 4-18, in which the relevant costs are plotted (operation, maintenance, CO₂, energy and costs related to specific technologies for the given variant). We can see the renewal of key technologies after 15 years, as well as the fact that the costs of the hybridGEOTABS variant grow slower over time.

Figure 4-18: Haus M – Cumulative costs for the basic scenario. Only costs for operation, maintenance, energies, CO₂ and technology specific investments are plotted

4.6. Conclusion

The simulations for Haus M multi-family building show that the heating and cooling delivered to the emission systems (and thereby to the building zones) is lower for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, mainly as a result of the control which allows for greater temperature gradients along the day and among the different building zones, of course within the thermal comfort limitations. The more stable indoor temperatures induced by the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* in this case lead to a higher energy use. In terms of ventilation, both scenarios have similar energy use and achieve the CO₂-concentration requirements.

The overall system efficiencies are higher for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario in heating and lower in cooling (2.7 in heating and 2.4 in cooling) than for the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (0.88 in heating and 4.62 in cooling). However, it is important to mention that the efficiencies of the GEOTABS system are on the low side, as the modelled heat pump has rather low COP's of 3.5 in heating and 2.5 in cooling, and the more energy-efficient option of passive cooling was not modelled. Therefore the results shown are rather conservative.

The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* leads to primary energy reductions of 48 % and CO₂-emission reductions of 62 % as compared to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC*, and assuming the electricity mix represents the EU average. However, when considering the Swiss electricity mix, which is more energy-efficient, and especially has lower CO₂-intensity, the reductions become 54 % in primary energy and even 91 % in CO₂-emissions. Both in relative and in absolute terms, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* building benefits much more from the change to a more energy-efficient and low-carbon electricity mix.

In terms of financial costs, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario life cycle cost is about 3 %, or about 570 000 CHF more expensive than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline, which is not a significant difference given the uncertainties of the calculations. As can be seen in [D5.5](#) (Cost Benefit Analysis), for some scenarios, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenarios are even cheaper than the baseline.

5. Analysis: Infrac/Fluvius office building

5.1. Building and scenarios

5.1.1. Infrac

Figure 5-1: Infrac – Pictures extracted from www.hybridgeotabs.eu

The Infrac building is a 2232 m² conditioned space four-story office building located in Brussels, Belgium. The building envelope model is composed of 27 zones, of which 21 are conditioned for heating and cooling. The 1st, 2nd and 3rd floors are mainly open plan offices and separate zones exist for the north and south spaces, the individual meeting rooms and the bathrooms (which are not conditioned). The ground floor includes individual conference rooms and several facilities (first aid room, canteen, storage and server rooms). The U-values for the outer walls and roof are between 0.18-0.25 and 0.14-0.15 W/m²/K respectively. The airtightness of the building is measured with a n₅₀ value of 1.3 ACH. The AHU is a centralized mechanical supply and exhaust ventilation with heat recovery provided by a thermal wheel which is located after the heating coil in the ventilation system. The scheme of the systems in the actual building is shown in Figure 5-2.

Figure 5-2: Infrac – Energy systems schematic

The virtual test-bed for Infrac considers the three scenarios that are shown in Figure 5-3. The two baselines (*hybridGEOTABS-RBC*, *nonGEOTABS-RBC*) and the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario were developed from the verified model that represents the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario.

Figure 5-3: Infrac – Scenarios scheme

5.1.2. As-Built scenario: *hybridGEOTABS_AB*

The *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario is the model that was verified with the available real data from the building. The measured data is stored by the Building Management System (BMS). The zoning of the building as included in the model is shown in Figure 5-4.

Figure 5-4: Infrac – Zoning

The verification took the temperatures of the zones, mass flows and other parameters of the HVAC system into account. A detailed explanation can be found in [D4.7](#).

5.1.3. Baselines: *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC*

The model of the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline is the same as the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario. The building envelope, the occupancy profiles and the internal heat gains are the same in all scenarios. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* differs from the as-built scenario in the weather conditions and the kind of RBC control, which has to consider the comfort conditions defined in 2.2.2 in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* again only differs from the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline in the control strategy. Finally, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* consist in the substitution of all the heating and cooling systems by systems with the characteristics described in 2.1.1. Table 5-1 shows the characteristics of all scenarios.

Table 5-1: Infrac – Similarities and differences of the different scenarios

Infrac	hybridGEOTABS_AB	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC	nonGEOTABS-RBC
Envelope	Infrac			
Occupancy	Occupancy profiles			
Weather	Brussels (measured data)	TMY Brussels		
Ventilation	Mechanical supply and extraction variable flow rate + CO ₂ control [900 ppm max]			
Heating system	GSHP → TABS (ceiling) + AHU + re-heating coils			Natural Gas Boiler → AHU + FCU
Heat recovery (heating)	Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)			Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)
Cooling system	TABS (ceiling) → Ground Heat Exchanger TABS			AHU + FCU → Chiller
Heat recovery (cooling)	Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)			Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)
DHW production	NO			
Control	as-built RBC	RBC hybridGEOTABS	MPC hybridGEOTABS	RBC nonGEOTABS

The weather conditions for the three scenarios in this comparison come from the typical meteorological year for Brussels, as presented in Figure 5-5. As the controls in all scenarios are based on the outdoor temperature, this parameter of the weather file used in the simulations is shown with its corresponding RMOT.

Figure 5-5: Infrac – Outdoor temperature and RMOT

5.2. Building behaviour

A night-setback is applied to the comfort bounds outside of the working hours. Figure 5-6 shows a 60-days period of the thermal comfort limits that are applicable to all scenarios. The graphical representation shows the transition due to the night-setback as vertical lines, where actually the change between modes is instantaneous.

Figure 5-6: Infrac – Detail of thermal comfort limits with setback in all scenarios

There are 21 conditioned zones, but the circulation zones like stairs or corridors and the zones with sporadic occupation, such as photocopy rooms or the first aid room, are excluded from the thermal comfort analysis, as explained in section 2.2.2. Figure 5-7 shows the temperature profiles of all conditioned zones that are in use (14) against the RMOT during the working hours, which represent 36 % of the hours of the simulated year. The vast majority of the temperatures fit between the comfort boundaries, with some exceptions that are represented mainly by outlier points.

All the scenarios respect the defined thermal comfort band. Looking at the shape of the violins, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* and *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenarios show a wider spread of the temperatures throughout the year (specially the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario) along the comfort band for each value of the RMOT, while the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario tends to concentrate the majority of the temperatures around one or two points. This feature is in line with the characteristics of TABS buildings, whose high inertia results in a slow change of the indoor conditions and thus a temperature drift caused by the presence of internal and external gains during the working hours. On the other hand, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline is equipped with individual FCUs per zone that allow fast and individual control. Despite the hybrid GEOTABS baselines are also equipped with a secondary system, the baseload is provided by the GEOTABS system which is controlled on a per-floor basis. Hence, the temperature differences between zones in the hybrid GEOTABS baselines can be larger. The temperature distribution of the hybrid GEOTABS-MPC baseline is wider than the hybrid GEOTABS-RBC baseline, indicating that MPC is harnessing the full temperature drift allowed by the temperature comfort bounds.

Infrac: Operative Temperature vs RMOT - 43848 points by scenario

Conditioned Zones: 14 | Working hours: 3132 (36 % of 8760 hours of the standard year)

Figure 5-7: Infrac – Operative temperature profiles vs RMOT

Figure 5-8 shows the time series corresponding to the data included in Figure 5-7. The data is filtered to show exclusively the temperatures and limits of the working hours (note the discontinuities). The limits are shown as continuous lines to make the comfort band easier to understand. The figure shows that the operative temperatures in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario do not reach the upper part of the comfort band during the heating season, while for the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC*, the operative temperatures are distributed along the full range of the comfort band in the same period. All scenarios present some small violations on the lower comfort limits, where the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* the scenario has the most significant violations along the year and the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* the scenario has the least violations. Regarding the overheating, all scenarios present certain violations of the upper comfort limits, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* is the scenario with the least violations, followed by the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario. In any case, all violations represent a small fraction of time, as it can be seen in Figure 5-8.

As additional information, Figure 5-9 shows a detailed view of the operative temperatures in a period of two months in Spring-Summer, including working and non-working days, and the thermal comfort limits with their setback. This view shows that the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has a faster reaction than the other two scenarios in the transitions between non-working and working days (for example, on 14th June, where *nonGEOTABS-RBC* can change the temperature quite fast). The TABS in both *hybridGEOTABS* scenarios continue to heat or cool the building during the non-working hours, behaviour that is reflected on the figure, where the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario shows a higher variation in the operative temperatures during the non-working hours (e.g. the days before 28th June). Some violations of the comfort limits appear after the mentioned transitions in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario (for example, on 31st May in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario). In any case, all scenarios follow the thermal comfort requirements.

Infrax - Operative temperatures (working hours)

Figure 5-8: Infrax – Operative temperatures of the conditioned zones and comfort bands for all scenarios (working hours)

Infrax - Operative temperatures (detail, all hours)

Figure 5-9: Infrax – Detail of operative temperatures, including working and non-working days

Infrax - CO₂ concentration (detail, all hours)

Figure 5-10: Infrax – CO₂-concentration (detail, all hours)

Figure 5-10 shows a two-months window of the CO₂-concentrations of the tracked zones. The rest of the year has a similar behaviour. The scenarios *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC* are below 900 ppm all the

simulation time. Most of the zones in the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* are also below this threshold, with the exception of the meeting and conference rooms. In these zones, the MPC relaxes the constraints using the slack variable applied to the CO₂ constraints. The exact cause for this relaxation could not be identified and should be investigated further. We estimate that increasing the flow rates to avoid this relaxation would require 650 kWh of fan energy, which is only 2.5% of the total electrical energy use of the building. Still, the obtained values fit well within the Category-II limits established in standard EN16798-1. Therefore, we consider the reported violations to be acceptable.

5.3. Energy performance

5.3.1. Energy flows

Figure 5-11, Figure 5-12 and Figure 5-13 show the Sankey diagrams associated to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC*, *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenarios. The energy demand of the building is represented as intense-coloured flows on the graphs. In the *hybridGEOTABS* scenarios they are the three flows for heating demand connected to the node named "Buffer" and two flows for cooling demand connected to the nodes "HEX TABS" and "HEX AHU". In the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario they are the two flows connected to the node called "Boiler" for heating and the two nodes connected to the node named "Chiller" for cooling.

In both *hybridGEOTABS* scenarios, there are flows that turn backwards from the nodes named "HEX TABS" and "HEX AHU", which represent energy that is extracted during cooling operation and injected in the building again through the GSHP. The characteristics of the *hybridGEOTABS* system in this building allow the building to share heat from zones that are slightly warmer to the colder zones by using the TABS circuit. Then, an internal heat flow appears for distributing the heat among the zones. On the Sankey diagrams, the distributed flow is represented as a recirculating flow: the heat is distributed from the blue node named "TABS" (which extracts heat from warmer zones) to the red node named "TABS" (which delivers heat to the colder zones). Further, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario barely uses the cooling tower. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario does not use the Cooling tower and the related nodes at all, so they were removed from the corresponding Sankey diagram.

Table 5-2 summarizes the information showed on the Sankey diagrams and Table 5-3 gives the derived efficiencies.

Figure 5-11: Infrac – Sankey diagram for the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario

PE factor electricity: 2 (kWh PE)/kWh

INFRAX

hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario

Main energy flows in the building (normalized by conditioned area)
Values in [kWh/m²/year]

Figure 5-12: Infrax – Sankey diagram for the hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario

PE factor electricity: 2 (kWh PE)/kWh

INFRAX

hybridGEOTABS-MPC scenario

Main energy flows in the building (normalized by conditioned area)
Values in [kWh/m²/year]

Figure 5-13: Infrax – Sankey diagram for the hybridGEOTABS-MPC scenario

Table 5-2: Infrax – Summary table extracted from the energy flows

Infrax - units in [kWh/m ² /year]	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Active injected heat (local space heating) - thermal energy	9.6	10.8	13.1
GEOTABS - thermal energy	0.0	7.0	8.1
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	4.0	2.9
nonGEOTABS - thermal energy	9.6	3.8	5.1
Electricity - electric energy	0.4	1.8	1.5
Natural gas - thermal energy	10.7	0.0	0.0
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) - thermal energy	6.3	8.5	2.0
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	4.0	2.0
Natural gas - thermal energy	7.0	0.0	0.0
Recovery heat from ventilation - thermal energy	15.4	18.1	14.8
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) - thermal energy	18.4	14.3	21.6
GEOTABS - thermal energy	0.0	14.3	21.6
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	2.7	2.8
nonGEOTABS - thermal energy	18.4	0.0	0.0
Electricity - electric energy	5.2	0.0	0.0
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) - thermal energy	0.9	3.0	5.2
Electricity - electric energy	0.2	0.5	1.0
Recovery heat from ventilation - thermal energy	0.0	0.1	0.1
Recirculated heat (simultaneous heating and cooling) - thermal energy	0.0	5.3	4.0
Net space heat ([space heating] - [space cooling]) - thermal energy	-3.4	2.0	-11.7
Ventilation (electricity fans) - electric energy	3.3	4.7	0.8
Total electricity - electric energy	9.1	17.7	11.0
Total natural gas - thermal energy	17.7	0.0	0.0
Primary energy (electricity: $\times 2$; gas: $\times 1.1$)	37.7	35.3	22.0

Table 5-3: Infrax – Efficiencies and GEOTABS share

Infrax - Efficiencies and GEOTABS share. Dimensionless	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Active injected heat (local space heating) (efficiency)	0.87	1.89	2.98
GEOTABS (SCOP system)		1.78	2.82
nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	0.87	2.12	3.26
Share GEOTABS	0%	65%	61%
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) (efficiency)	0.90	2.10	0.98
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) (efficiency)	3.53	5.22	7.64
GEOTABS (SCOP system)		5.22	7.64
nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	3.53	0.00	
Share GEOTABS	0%	100%	100%
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) (efficiency)	4.09	6.01	5.31
Global efficiency heating+pre-heating	0.88	1.97	2.35
Global share GEOTABS heating + pre-heating		37%	53%
GSHP SCOP space heating (component)		3.08	5.14
Global efficiency cooling+pre-cooling	3.56	5.34	7.04
Global share GEOTABS cooling + pre-cooling		83%	81%
GSHP SCOP cooling (component)		4.00	only passive cooling
Global efficiency space heating and cooling	1.50	2.81	4.10

Figure 5-14 shows the heating and cooling demands and the heat recovery of the ventilation. The net space heating is quite different in all scenarios, one reason being the different ventilation rates between the scenarios. Regarding the heat recovery in the ventilation system, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenarios recover almost the same amount of heat, but the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* requires about three times the amount of electricity for the AHU (see Table 5-2), due to the higher flow rates used in ventilation. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario also has increased ventilation and thus higher electricity use, and recovers 22 % more heat from the ventilation air. The re-heating coils in the hybridGEOTABS scenarios (the node called ReHea Coils in Figure 5-12 and Figure 5-13) are connected to the AHU, so they require the ventilation fans to run to be able to heat up or cool down the zones. This is the reason to have the different values in the ventilation electricity use in this building. If the re-heating coils were connected to FCUs, the ventilation and the heat recovery would be similar in all scenarios.

Looking at the active space heating and cooling, taking place via active pre-heating/cooling of the ventilation supply air and via the nonGEOTABS and GEOTABS heating/cooling, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario requires about 15.9 kWh/m²/year of heating and 19.3 kWh/m²/year of cooling, which is slightly above the requirements for

passive houses in the heating case (15 kWh/m²/year). This generally confirms the overall energy-efficiency of the building. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario uses about 21.3 % more heating and 10.4 % less cooling than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, which can be partially explained by (i) the increased ventilation rates triggered by simultaneous heating and cooling in the RBC and (ii) the storage capabilities of TABS, which initially require a massive amount of energy to activate the building (and especially taking into account that the simulation starts in the middle of the heating season), which is thus a cold start. Once activated, TABS can harness its buffer effect to extract heat from the building as soon as the indoor conditions increase above the concrete temperature. This feature is observed as well in the Sankey diagrams. On the contrary, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario requires 5 % less heating than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, but also significantly more cooling (+44 %). This increase in cooling is caused by the loss of optimality due to the used post-processing of the MPC. MPC tends to use lower TABS supply temperatures compared to RBC to keep the zone temperatures near the lower comfort limit in order to anticipate the upcoming external and internal gains during the working hours. However, by doing so and since there is a mismatch between the simulation and the controller model, the lower limit comfort bound is sometimes violated, which triggers the hysteresis controller of the re-heating coils and the air is supplied at maximum temperature. As a consequence, heating and cooling is provided simultaneously, producing a recirculation of heat through the heat pump evaporator, and more heat needs to be extracted. This hysteresis controller was added as an extra fast-reacting control layer to keep the comfort within the boundaries and the violations below the established threshold. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario also tends to make more use of the GEOTABS part of the system in heating, that is 53 % of the active space heating requirements instead of 36 % for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. In cooling, for both scenarios about 80 % is covered by GEOTABS.

Figure 5-14: Infrac – Heat delivered/extracted to/from the building (per sub-system)

Table 5-2 documents how much electricity and natural gas are needed to provide the required heating, cooling and ventilation to the building, and Table 5-3 presents the associated system efficiencies, showing that the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario has the highest efficiencies, while the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario is the least efficient in all categories. Looking at the GEOTABS system, the SCOP is higher for the MPC control compared to the RBC control (from 1.78 to 2.82 in heating and from 5.22 to 7.64 in cooling). The COP of the heat pump itself is 5.4. The SCOP of the heat pump is 6.99 and 9.08 in heating for the RBC and MPC respectively, showing the increased performances of TABS systems as they work at lower supply temperatures. However, the effect of simultaneous heating and cooling (which causes higher evaporator temperatures in the GSHP) also contributes to these increased SCOPs. The auxiliary pumps P₀₁ and P₀₃ are not accounted in this SCOP calculation. The GEOTABS cooling consists of active and passive cooling. It is also very noticeable the energy share of the pumping system in the hybrid GEOTABS cases, pinpointing that it should not be neglected in large and complex systems. The share of pump energy is 58% in the hybrid GEOTABS-RBC baseline and 75% in the hybrid GEOTABS-MPC baseline, as most of the pumps retain their original RBC in this case. Future efforts should incorporate the pump power and control in the MPC optimization problem. Also note the lower pumping energy use in the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline, since no pressure drops could be modelled with real information. The electric powers of each of the 12 modelled pumps in the hybrid GEOTABS baselines range between 0.3 and 2.2 kW, while the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline the maximum of the 5 pumps is limited to 0.35 kW. Based on this observation, the energy savings calculated are considered to be in the conservative side. Using a linear extrapolation, we estimate the electricity use of the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline pumps between 3.2 kWh/m²/year and 3.8 kWh/m²/year.

5.3.2. Primary energy use

Figure 5-15 and Figure 5-16 show the corresponding primary energy use of the three scenarios, the former one assuming the average EU electricity mix, and the latter one assuming the local Belgian electricity mix, using primary energy factors as listed in Table 3-3. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario proves to be the overall most energy-efficient scenario, by using about 38% less primary energy than the other two scenarios. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has a primary energy performance similar to the one of the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, assuming today's electricity mixes. This is explained due to the electricity/gas factor ratio, which unfortunately benefits the use of the gas source. The maximum electricity/gas factor ratio to increase the energy savings compared to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline is 2.07 for the hybrid GEOTABS-RBC baseline and 6.59 for the hybrid GEOTABS-MPC baseline, demonstrating the importance of optimal control when using complex HVAC systems.

Figure 5-15: Infrac – Primary energy (per sub-system) using EU factors

Figure 5-16: Infrac – Primary energy (per sub-system) using local factors

Figure 5-17 and Figure 5-18 show the primary energy use with the average EU primary energy factors against the equivalent outdoor temperature. The first figure represents the data for the working days, while the second one shows the non-working days. The figures show different behaviour that confirms the division in the type of days. Regarding the working days, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario uses, in general, less primary energy than the other two scenarios throughout all the seasons. The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario uses more energy than the other two in the coldest and warmest periods of the year, mainly as a result of the less efficient systems used and not being able to store energy in the concrete. The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario also has a similar or lower primary energy use than the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario when equivalent outdoor temperatures are between about 10°C and 15°C. In these periods the energy use of the ventilation system becomes more dominant than the

heating and cooling requirements, and at the same time it is a challenging period for the control of the HVAC, with more risks of having parts of the system working against each other while pursuing to maintain thermal comfort in the building. The MPC can handle in a more efficient way than the RBC.

During non-working days, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario does not use energy, except in warmer periods, which may be explained by an activation of the cooling system when the non-working days comfort limits are exceeded. The hybridGEOTABS scenarios do consume energy also on non-working days, as the GEOTABS system works all the time due to the thermal inertia of the TABS. Again, the MPC does this in the more energy-efficient manner.

Figure 5-17: Infrac – Energy signature (primary energy with EU factors) - working days

Figure 5-18: Infrac – Energy signature (primary energy with EU factors) - non-working days

Finally, Table 5-4 documents the balance of the ground for the geothermal heat pump. In the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, there is an almost perfect balance between the heat injected and extracted from the ground over the course of one year. In the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario, about twice as much energy is injected than there is extracted. In addition, the ground (injection) peak loads are quantified as 49.3 kW for the hybrid GEOTABS-RBC and 62.8 kW for the hybrid GEOTABS-MPC. Figure 5 19 addresses the long-term feasibility of the hybrid GEOTABS baselines with the current size and whether this size ought to be increased or reduced with the new loads obtained by dynamic simulation. The obtained yearly ground loads are applied to the borefield model and this is repeated for 25 years. We set an upper borefield outlet temperature limit of 18 C since this is the temperature threshold that triggers active cooling in the RBC, and a lower borefield outlet

temperature limit of -2 C based on the propylene glycol mixture used. The left axis (solid line) corresponds to the borefield outlet fluid temperature, indicating that the borefield is oversized for both baselines as it is far from reaching the design limits. This was expected since in practice the borefield also needs to provide the cooling load of the installed server units. The right axis (dashed line) plots the yearly moving average of the difference between the outlet fluid temperature and the undisturbed ground temperature, showing the increased effect of the thermal imbalance in the hybrid GEOTABS-MPC baseline.

Table 5-4: Infrac – Ground balance

Infrac - Ground balance	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Heat extracted from the ground [kWh/m ² /year]	14.58	9.48
Heat delivered to the ground [kWh/m ² /year]	15.33	23.16
Ground balance ((heat extracted)-[heat delivered]) [kWh/m ² /year]	-0.75	-13.69
Ground balance ratio ((heat extracted)/[heat delivered]) [-]	0.95	0.41

Figure 5-19: Thermal balance of the geothermal borefield for the hybrid GEOTABS baselines after 25 years

5.4. Environmental performance

Figure 5-20 and Figure 5-21 show the CO₂-emissions with the EU and local conversion factors (remark that the Belgian electricity mix is clearly less CO₂-intensive than the EU average). The hybridGEOTABS scenarios emit a significantly lower amount of CO₂ than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, with reduction of 26.6 % and 76.4 %, dependent on the electricity used. The MPC allows a further reduction with about 37.7 % as compared to the RBC scenario with both conversion factors, to less than 1 (kg CO₂)/m²/year in the case of using the Belgian factor.

Figure 5-20: Infrax – CO₂-emissions (EU factor)

Figure 5-21: Infrax – CO₂-emissions (local factor)

5.5. Cost performance

For the cost performance of the Infrax building and for the three variants, we have assumed the following additional inputs:

Table 5-5: Infrac – cost categories

Input	nonGT-RBC	hGT-RBC	hGT-MPC
Basic construction costs	6 026 400 EUR	6 026 400 EUR	6 026 400 EUR
Extra technologies	516 192 EUR	592 981 EUR	592 981 EUR
Design fees	53 492 EUR	72 149 EUR	74 439 EUR
Gas boiler	18 600 EUR	–	–
Heat pump (incl. chillers)	94 586 EUR	122 137 EUR	122 137 EUR
Borefield cost	–	135 061 EUR	135 61 EUR
Automation (+MPC)	83 850 EUR	111 809 EUR	142 337 EUR
Electricity price	0.28 EUR/kWh	0.28 EUR/kWh	0.28 EUR/kWh
Discount rate	1.5 %	1.5 %	1.5 %
CO₂ price	50 EUR/ton	50 EUR/ton	50 EUR/ton

We have also assumed the local energy conversion ratios.

Based on the EC Regulation No. 244/2012, we performed the cost benefit analysis with the following results:

Table 5-6: Infrac – Global cost calculated (Net Present Value)

Variant		nonGT-RBC	hGT-RBC	hGT-MPC
Initial investment cost		6 793 120 EUR	6 793 120 EUR	6 793 120 EUR
Annual running cost	7 313 EUR	5 688 EUR	6 500 EUR	6 500 EUR
	5 332 EUR	6 331 EUR	7 157 EUR	20 475 EUR
	8 738 EUR	8 971 EUR	5 586 EUR	6 367 EUR
Calculation period		30	30	30
Cost of greenhouse gas emissions		12 024 EUR	2 829 EUR	1 768 EUR
Residual value		978 324 EUR	978 324 EUR	978 324 EUR
Discount rate		1,50%	1,50%	1,50%
Estimated economic lifetime		30	30	30
Disposal cost		N/A	N/A	N/A
Global cost calculated (NPV)		7 038 005 EUR	7 379 869 EUR	7 361 516 EUR

The hybridGEOTABS systems have bigger life cycle cost (LCC) than the non-GEOTABS variant – however, the difference is again not significant, only 323 510 EUR, which is about 4.4 % of the life cycle cost and comparable to the 3 % found for Haus M. The sensitivity of the results is smaller than for Haus M and hybridGEOTABS variants tend to be more expensive for most of the scenarios (for details, see D5.5 – Cost Benefit Analysis).

It is also interesting to look at the cumulative costs of the basic scenario – this is shown in Figure 5-22, wherein the relevant costs are plotted (operation, maintenance, CO₂, energy and costs related to specific technologies for the given variant). We can see the renewal of key technologies after 15 years, as well as the fact that the costs of the hybridGEOTABS variant grow slower over time. It is also interesting that the life cycle costs of the MPC variant is lower than the RBC variant, in addition to the other advantages of MPC.

Figure 5-22: Infrac – cumulative costs for the basic scenario. Only costs for operation, maintenance, energies, CO₂ and technology specific investments are plotted. A variant with photovoltaics was also investigated (for details, see D5.5).

5.6. Additional sensitivity analysis of the energy weighting factors

Ultimately, the primary energy use, the CO₂-emissions and the operational costs are expressed as a function of the building energy use, where the various energy vectors are weighted differently using the primary energy factor, the carbon intensity and the prices. The proportion between these (primary energy, emissions or cost) weighting factors determines the relative savings of the different baselines, while their magnitude affects the absolute savings. Figure 5-23 shows the relative savings of the hybridGEOTABS scenarios compared to the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline as a function of the electricity/gas weighting factor ratio c_r , showing large variations among the different contexts (indicated by vertical lines). Lower electricity/gas weighting factor ratios penalize the use of gas-driven components, ergo the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline. This is especially the case for the Belgian emission factor ratio, while oddly enough the cost factor ratio is unrelated thus penalizing electricity. The hybridGEOTABS-RBC baseline and the hybridGEOTABS-MPC baseline stop performing better than the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline at a weighting factor ratio of 2.07 and 6.59 respectively. It is clear that this weighting factor ratio, which is location dependent, is crucial towards design and performance evaluation of the results.

Figure 5-23: Infrac – hybrid GEOTABS-RBC and hybrid GEOTABS-MPC savings relative to the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline as a function of electricity/gas factor ratio.

5.7. Conclusions

The simulations for the Infrac office building show that the heat delivered for space heating is influenced by the ventilation rates as well as the heat extracted for space cooling. The lower ventilation rates in the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario leads to a higher cooling demand than in any of the other scenarios, while the heating demand is the lowest. The higher ventilation rates in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario reduce the cooling demand to the minimum of the three scenarios, but also increase the heating demand significantly, causing this scenario to be the most heat-demanding. Regarding the CO₂-concentration, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* has a worse behaviour than the other two scenarios, showing higher concentrations of carbon dioxide along the year. The ability of the MPC to control the ventilation flowrates may be used to find a better balance between the energy saving, the overheating of the building and the quality of the air. In other words, the penalties involved in the optimization problem need to be adjusted to accomplish the same levels of CO₂-concentration.

The overall system efficiencies in heating show the clear advantage of the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario, with a ratio of 2.35, over the other two scenarios (0.88 in *nonGEOTABS-RBC* and 1.97 in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*). The global efficiency for space cooling follows a similar behaviour, being 7.04 in *hybridGEOTABS-MPC*, 5.34 in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and 3.56 in *nonGEOTABS-RBC*. The combination of heating and cooling efficiencies are 4.10 in *hybridGEOTABS-MPC*, 2.81 in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and 1.50 in *nonGEOTABS-RBC*. Again, the scenario with the MPC control has the highest efficiency and the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* the lowest.

The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* leads to primary energy reductions of about 38% as compared to the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*, thanks to a more efficient control strategy. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC* have similar primary energy use for the given primary energy factors, knowing that the Belgian mix is not very energy efficient and close to the EU average factors. The situation is different for the CO₂-emissions, where the Belgian electricity mix is clearly less carbon-intensive than the EU average. There, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario emits 27% to 76% less CO₂, and the MPC-scenario allows a further reduction with about 38%.

In terms of financial costs, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario life cycle cost is about 4.4%, or about 323 510 EUR more expensive than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline, which is not a significant difference given the uncertainties of the calculations. The MPC variant is slightly cheaper than the RBC variant in terms of life cycle costs.

6. Analysis: Libeznice school

The simulations of the Libeznice school model were not finalised in time and the results are therefore not included in this report.

7. Analysis: Ter Potterie elderly care home

7.1. Building and scenarios

Figure 7-1: Ter Potterie elderly home: picture

The Ter Potterie building is a 10 048 m² conditioned space (16 103 m² gross floor area) elderly care home building located in Bruges, Belgium. This building mostly contains single bedrooms but also common living rooms, offices, a kitchen, a cafeteria, and some rooms for staff. To reduce the size of the model, rooms of similar type, located at the same level and adjacent to each other, and of identical orientation were lumped together if they are connected to a same air handling unit. The resulting model is composed by 27 conditioned and 13 unconditioned zones.

All conditioned rooms have floor heating and/or TABS, except the kitchen and the polyvalent room. Additionally, all rooms are equipped with radiators sized such that they can cover approximately 30 % of the heat losses at nominal conditions. The scheme of the systems in the actual building is shown in Figure 7-2.

Figure 7-2: Ter Potterie – Energy systems schematic

The virtual test-bed for Ter Potterie considers the three scenarios that are shown in Figure 7-3. The two baselines (*hybridGEOTABS-RBC*, *nonGEOTABS-RBC*) and the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario were developed from the verified model that represents the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario.

Figure 7-3: Ter Potterie – Scenarios scheme

7.1.1. As-Built scenario: *hybridGEOTABS_AB*

As in the rest of the cases, the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario is the model that was verified with the available real data from the building. The measured data is stored by the Building Management System (BMS). Further details of the modelling of the building can be found in [D4.7](#).

7.1.2. Baselines: *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and *nonGEOTABS-RBC*

The model of the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline is the same as the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario. The building envelope, the occupancy profiles and the internal heat gains are the same in all scenarios. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* differs from the as-built scenario in the weather conditions and the kind of RBC control, which has to consider the comfort conditions defined in 2.2.2. Regarding the weather conditions, the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* has the conditions used for the verification of the model, while the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline has the typical meteorological year, as do the other two scenarios. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* differs from the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* baseline in the control strategy. Finally, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* consist in the substitution of all the heating and cooling systems by systems with the characteristics described in 2.1.1. Table 7-1 shows the characteristics of all scenarios. Note that each scenario has its own control strategy.

Table 7-1: Ter Potterie – Similarities and differences of the different scenarios

Ter Potterie	hybridGEOTABS_AB	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC	nonGEOTABS-RBC
Envelope	Ter Potterie			
Occupancy	Occupancy profiles			
Weather	Bruges (measured data)	TMY Brussels		
Ventilation	Mechanical supply and extraction fixed flow rate			
Heating system	GSHP → TABS (ceiling) + Floor Heating Natural Gas Boiler → AHU + Radiators			Natural Gas Boiler → AHU + FCU
Heat recovery (heating)	Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)			Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)
Cooling system	TABS (ceiling) + Floor cooling + AHU → Ground Heat Exchanger			AHU + FCU → Chiller
Heat recovery (cooling)	Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)			Thermal Wheel (Heat Exchanger Air-Air)
DHW production	Natural Gas Boiler	NO		NO
Control	as-built RBC	RBC hybridGEOTABS	MPC hybridGEOTABS	RBC nonGEOTABS

The weather conditions for the three scenarios in this comparison come from the typical meteorological year for Brussels, while the comfort boundaries are defined according to section 2.2.2. As the controls in all scenarios are based on the outdoor temperature, this parameter of the weather file used in the simulations is shown with its corresponding RMOT in Figure 7-4.

Figure 7-4: Ter Potterie – Outdoor temperature and RMOT

The selected simulation results start on day 10 and finish on the day 375 (note the dates on Figure 7-4).

7.2. Building behaviour

As the building is continuously in use, it has a single operation mode, like the multi-family building Haus M. The comfort limits are activated permanently without any setback period.

Figure 7-5 shows the distributions of the operative temperatures against the RMOT for all the scenarios and all conditioned zones. The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has lower operative temperatures in warmer periods, distributed on the lower half of the comfort band when $RMOT > 15\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. When $RMOT < 15\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the temperatures are distributed along full the comfort band. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario uses, in general, the comfort bounds more completely than the other scenarios. In this scenario, the operative temperatures are distributed along the comfort band throughout the seasons, showing concentrated points around the underheat soft limit when $RMOT < 11\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This behaviour indicates that the heating system successfully keeps the operative temperatures of the coldest zones in the thermal comfort range. Finally, the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario shows that the operative temperatures are less distributed than the other two scenarios, especially during winter, when $RMOT < 11\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This is also visible in the time series of the operative temperatures for all zones as shown in Figure 7-6

and reflects the typical behaviour of a classical RBC in buildings with fast-reacting emission systems (as opposed to the buildings with GEOTABS).

Ter Potterie: Operative Temperature vs RMOT - 227760 points by scenario
Conditioned Zones: 26 | Working hours: 8760 (100 % of 8760 hours of the standard year)

Figure 7-5: Ter Potterie – Operative temperature profiles vs RMOT

Ter Potterie - Operative temperatures

Figure 7-6: Ter Potterie – Operative temperatures of the conditioned zones and comfort bands for all scenarios (working hours)

The ventilation rates are the same in all scenarios, including the *hybridGEOTABS_AB* scenario, and equivalent to those in the actual building. The ventilation flow rates are fixed to 31000 m³/h, chosen in line with the function of the building as an elderly home, where high flow rates are often used in order to meet high indoor air quality standards. As we will see in the results, the high ventilation requirements have a significant influence on the energy performance of the building, and reduce the playfield of the MPC. While in the previous case-study building Infrac/Fluvius, the MPC could adapt the ventilation flow rates dependent on the CO₂-concentrations, the heating and cooling demands, in the Ter Potterie building the (higher) flow rates remain fixed.

7.3. Energy performance

7.3.1. Energy flows

Figure 7-7, Figure 7-8 and Figure 7-9 show the Sankey diagrams of the three scenarios. The energy demand is represented as intense-coloured flows. In both hybridGEOTABS scenarios they are the flows that connect the red nodes "Gas boiler" to "AHU", "Radiators" (only in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*) and "GSHP" to "TABS" and "Floor Heating", for heating, and the blue nodes "AHU", "TABS" and "Floor Cooling" to "HEX", for cooling. There is a part of the heat that recirculates through the TABS system from slightly warm zones to the colder ones, represented by the flow that connects the blue node "Heat extracted" to the red node "TABS".

The building is heating-dominated (e.g. because of the higher indoor temperatures required) and the impact of the ventilation is clearly visible, both in the electricity use (mainly by the fans) and the amount of heat used by its heating coil. Note that the ventilation is not meant for temperature control. It operates at constant flow and it is used isothermally, i.e. the supply air temperature is 21°C in the winter and 24°C in the summer. While the RBC control keeps these set points fixed for all rooms, MPC has the (only) additional freedom to lower it to 18°C for the day rooms and the offices.

Apart from feeding the ventilation heating coil and the FCUs (in the nonGEOTABS-scenario), the gas boiler also feeds the radiators in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. Nevertheless, the impact of this emission system is anecdotic in the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* system (it represents less than 2.5 % of the heat produced by the gas boiler and less than 1 % of the total heat produced for heating by the HVACR system). In the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario the radiators are not used, so they are not visible on the Sankey diagrams. In the hybridGEOTABS scenarios the GEOTABS system consists of the GSHP and GSHX providing heating and cooling to the TABS and the underfloor heating system. On the cooling side, the GSHX also supplies the pre-cooling of the ventilation supply air.

Table 7-2 summarizes the data in the Sankey diagrams and Table 7-3 summarises the system efficiencies.

Figure 7-7: Ter Potterie – Sankey diagram for the nonGEOTABS-RBC scenario

Figure 7-8: Ter Potterie – Sankey diagram for the hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario

Figure 7-9: Ter Potterie – Sankey diagram for the hybridGEOTABS-MPC scenario

Table 7-2: Ter Potterie – Summary table extracted from the energy flows

Ter Potterie - units in [kWh/m ² /year]	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Active injected heat (local space heating) - thermal energy	12.1	12.3	14.8
GEOTABS - thermal energy	0.0	12.1	14.8
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	3.5	4.2
nonGEOTABS - thermal energy	12.1	0.3	0.0
Electricity - electric energy	0.3	0.0	0.0
Natural gas - thermal energy	12.1	0.3	0.0
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) - thermal energy	19.9	20.6	18.0
Electricity - electric energy	0.2	0.3	0.3
Natural gas - thermal energy	19.9	21.1	18.4
Recovery heat from ventilation - thermal energy	47.9	49.4	48.8
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) - thermal energy	3.8	3.4	2.0
GEOTABS - thermal energy	0.0	3.4	2.0
Electricity - electric energy	0.0	0.4	0.4
nonGEOTABS - thermal energy	3.8	0.0	0.0
Electricity - electric energy	1.1	0.0	0.0
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) - thermal energy	0.4	0.4	0.6
Electricity - electric energy	0.1	0.0	0.0
Recovery heat from ventilation - thermal energy	0.0	0.0	0.2
Recirculated heat (simultaneous heating and cooling) - thermal energy	0.0	0.4	0.4
Net space heat ([space heating] - [space cooling]) - thermal energy	27.7	29.1	30.3
Ventilation (electricity fans) - electric energy	17.1	17.1	17.1
Total electricity - electric energy	18.8	21.4	22.1
Total natural gas - thermal energy	32.0	21.3	18.4
Primary energy (electricity: $\times 2$; gas: $\times 1.1$)	72.8	66.3	64.5

Table 7-3: Ter Potterie – Efficiencies and GEOTABS share

Ter Potterie - Efficiencies and GEOTABS share. Dimensionless	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Active injected heat (local space heating) (efficiency)	0.98	3.24	3.52
GEOTABS (SCOP system)		3.43	3.52
nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	0.98	0.97	
Share GEOTABS	0%	98%	100%
Pre-heating ventilation (global space heating) (efficiency)	0.99	0.97	0.96
Active extracted heat (local space cooling) (efficiency)	3.43	7.97	4.60
GEOTABS (SCOP system)		7.97	4.60
nonGEOTABS (efficiency)	3.43		
Share GEOTABS	0%	100%	100%
Pre-cooling ventilation (global space cooling) (efficiency)	3.66	67.48	45.02
Global efficiency heating+pre-heating	0.98	1.31	1.43
Global share GEOTABS heating + pre-heating		37%	45%
GSHP SCOP space heating (component)		6.24	5.76
Global efficiency cooling+pre-cooling	3.45	8.84	5.80
Global share GEOTABS cooling + pre-cooling		89%	77%
GSHP SCOP cooling (component)		only passive cooling	only passive cooling
Global efficiency space heating and cooling	1.07	1.44	1.52

Figure 7-10 presents the yearly heat exchanged with the conditioned zones via the GEOTABS and nonGEOTABS system parts, via pre-heating of the ventilation air and via heat recovery in the ventilation system. In each scenario, almost 50 kWh/m²/year is recovered in the ventilation system and roughly 32 kWh/m²/year is provided via active heating (incl. active pre-heating of the ventilation supply air). There are small differences between the scenarios, as the hybridGEOTABS scenarios require about 3.2 % and 2.9 % more heating than the nonGEOTABS-RBC scenario. The cooling requirements are very low, about 4.2 kWh/m²/year for the nonGEOTABS-RBC, and 3.8 kWh/m²/year and 2.6 kWh/m²/year for the hybridGEOTABS-RBC and -MPC respectively. In hybridGEOTABS scenarios they are provided mainly by the TABS and floor heating system (for more than 75 %), while the remainder is provided by the pre-cooling of ventilation air. In heating mode, GEOTABS provides 37 % of the active heating when using RBC, and 45 % when using MPC while the remaining energy is used to heat up the supply air to 22°C (18°C for day and office rooms for MPC). MPC uses its extra freedom by lowering the supply air temperature during the winter and thereby offsetting this heat load to the heat pump through the TABS, increasing the share of renewable energy.

In general, looking at the global figures, the three scenarios have a similar behaviour. However, *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* seems to have a slightly better use of the heat, meaning that this scenario requires less movements of heat for heating and cooling to guarantee the thermal comfort.

Figure 7-10: Ter Potterie – Heat delivered/extracted to/from the building (per sub-system)

By comparing the required heating and cooling to the electricity and natural gas used to provide them, the overall system efficiencies can be estimated (Table 7-3). The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario remains the most efficient scenario when looking at the overall heating system (1.31 in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*, 1.43 in *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* and 0.98 in *nonGEOTABS-RBC*), while the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario seems to perform better during cooling operation (8.84 in *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*, 5.80 in *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* and 3.45 in *nonGEOTABS-RBC*). As cooling represents a minor part of the building demands, the global system efficiency is highest in the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario and lowest in the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. It is noticeable that the electricity used by the circulation pumps (reduced to the closest nodes on the Sankey diagrams) has a great impact on the different efficiencies obtained in all scenarios.

Looking at the GEOTABS system, the SCOP is higher for the MPC control compared to the RBC control, from 3.43 to 3.52 in heating. The SCOP of the heat pump is 6.24 and 5.76 in heating for the RBC and MPC respectively. The GEOTABS cooling and pre-cooling of the ventilation air consist entirely of passive cooling via the heat exchanger. This is a very energy-efficient process only requiring electricity to feed the circulation pumps of the geothermal borefield. In the system efficiencies, the pumps of the TABS and of the cooling coils to the AHU are

also included, leading to a GEOTABS SCOP of 8 with RBC and 4.6 with MPC, and a pre-cooling SCOP of a factor 10 higher³. Again, the different figures are influenced by the effect of the circulation pumps.

7.3.2. Primary energy use

Figure 7-11 and Figure 7-12 show the primary energy use of all scenarios with the primary energy factors for the EU and for Belgium. As both primary energy factors are in the same order of magnitude, the outcomes are similar. Focusing on the EU factors, about 8.9 % primary energy savings are obtained by changing the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* for a *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, and another 2.7 % by replacing the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* for a *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario. These seemingly low savings are due to the large amount of heat required by the ventilation to lift the ventilation supply temperature to the comfort temperature. In order to quantify the percentage of savings achieved by MPC, one should focus on what MPC is allowed to optimize: the amount of energy used for space heating and shifting the heat load required by the ventilation from the heating coil to the TABS by supplying the ventilation at a colder temperature and thereby covering this load with the TABS. Table 7-4 summarizes the primary energy flows required for space heating and the ventilation for the EU and local factors. The percentage savings is calculated by comparing the required energy for space heating after subtracting the additional heating due to the shift from the ventilation to the space heating. The results shows that MPC saves between 15 to 21% of the primary energy used for space heating, depending on the primary energy factors.

Table 7-4: Comparison of the primary energy use by MPC and RBC for the HybridGEOTABS scenarios

		EU factors		Local factors	
		MPC	RBC	MPC	RBC
Heating GEOTABS (space heating)	[kWh/m ² /y]	8.43	7.04	10.12	8.45
Pre-heating ventilation	[kWh/m ² /y]	20.85	23.75	20.97	23.87
Savings on space heating	[kWh/m ² /y]	-1.39	-	-1.67	-
Savings on ventilation	[kWh/m ² /y]	2.9	-	2.9	-
Total savings	[kWh/m ² /y]	1.51	-	1.23	-
Percentage savings on space heating: Total savings / space heating RBC	[-]	21%		15%	

³ Remark that the electricity of the fans in the AHU is accounted for in the electricity use for ventilation, and not in the pre-cooling function.

Figure 7-11: Ter Potterie – Primary energy (per sub-system) using EU factors

Figure 7-12: Ter Potterie – Primary energy (per sub-system) using local factors

The Figure 7-13 shows the primary energy use in function of the equivalent outdoor temperature. A fixed 'baseload' of the ventilation fans, of about 100 Wh/(m².day) is observed for the three scenarios throughout all the seasons. The heating period starts when $T_{eq} < 17$ °C, which is a rather high temperature. Also, very little additional energy for cooling in summer times is observed.

The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario uses, in general, more primary energy than any of the *hybridGEOTABS* scenarios. Both *hybridGEOTABS* have a very similar behaviour. In this case, as the distributions are very similar, it is convenient to use statistical tools to determine if they are significantly different or not. The paired Wilcoxon test gives a p-value of $2E-23$ using the default 'two-sided' alternative hypothesis. Hence, the null hypothesis at a confidence level of 5 % ($p\text{-value} = 2E-23 \ll 0.05$), concluding that there is a difference in both distributions of the

hybridGEOTABS scenarios. A further test can be performed to check whether the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* has lower values than the RBC control. Then, the alternative hypothesis is that the MPC is lower than the RBC scenario, giving a p-value of 1, confirming that the distribution of the primary energy use in the MPC control is significantly lower than in the other control.

Figure 7-13: Ter Potterie – Energy signature (primary energy with EU factors) - working days

Table 7-5 shows the ground balance for the hybridGEOTABS scenarios. In both scenarios there is a significant imbalance of the heat injected and extracted from the borefield. The imbalance is inherent to Ter Potterie, as it is a heating-dominated building. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario shows a greater imbalance compared to the RBC scenario by extracting more heat from the ground (12.27 kWh/m²/year with MPC and 10.13 kWh/m²/year with RBC) and injecting less heat into the ground (2.59 kWh/m²/year with MPC and 3.86 kWh/m²/year with RBC). Consequently, the risk of depletion of the borefield is higher in the MPC scenario. However, the borefield has been sized accordingly.

Table 7-5: Ter Potterie – Ground balance

Ter Potterie - Ground balance	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Heat extracted from the ground [kWh/m ² /year]	10.13	12.27
Heat delivered to the ground [kWh/m ² /year]	3.86	2.59
Ground balance (([heat extracted]-[heat delivered]) [kWh/m ² /year]	6.27	9.68
Ground balance ratio (([heat extracted])/[heat delivered]) [-]	2.62	4.74

7.4. Environmental performance

The CO₂-emissions are shown on Figure 7-14 and Figure 7-15, using the EU average and local conversion factors as defined in Table 3-3. As with the primary energy use, it is important to remark that a significant part of the CO₂-emissions stems from functions that remain unaltered between the scenarios, such as those related to the electricity for the ventilation fans. Therefore, the savings on the 'influenced' parts are worth mentioning as well. As in the previous analysis, by neglecting the ventilation function, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* shows a reduction of 22.5 % and 30.7 % respect to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, while the hybridGEOTABS shows a reduction of 8 % and 12.2 % respect to the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario and 28.7 % and 39.2 % respect to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, using the EU and the Belgian conversion factors, respectively. Looking finally at the overall system, when the Belgian situation with its less carbon-intensive electricity mix, CO₂-emission reductions of 27 % are observed when replacing the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* by a *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*, and another 10 % by adapting the RBC for an MPC (assuming the EU factors). As with the other case-study buildings, the hybridGEOTABS buildings profit more from the shift to a cleaner electricity mix.

Figure 7-14: Ter Potterie – CO₂-emissions (EU factor)

Figure 7-15: Ter Potterie – CO₂-emissions (local factor)

7.5. Cost performance

For the cost performance of Ter Potterie and for the three variants, we have assumed the following additional inputs:

Table 7-6: Ter Potterie – Cost categories

Input	nonGT-RBC	hGT-RBC	hGT-MPC
Basic construction costs	27 129 600 EUR	27 129 600 EUR	27 129 600 EUR
Extra technologies	1 815 311 EUR	1 837 368 EUR	1 837 368 EUR
Design fees	139 908 EUR	162 250 EUR	170 170 EUR
Gas boiler	54 500 EUR	37 120 EUR	37 120 EUR
Heat pump (incl. chillers)	268 035 EUR	283 030 EUR	283 030 EUR
Borefield cost	–	354 434 EUR	354 434 EUR
Automation (+MPC)	193 955 EUR	192 215 EUR	242 215 EUR
Electricity price	0.28 EUR/kWh	0.28 EUR/kWh	0.28 EUR/kWh
Discount rate	1.5 %	1.5 %	1.5 %
CO₂ price	50 EUR/ton	50 EUR/ton	50 EUR/ton

We have also assumed the local energy conversion ratios.

Based on the EC Regulation No. 244/2012, we performed the cost benefit analysis with the following results:

Table 7-7: Ter Potterie – Global cost calculated (Net Present Value)

Variant		nonGT-RBC	hGT-RBC	hGT-MPC
Initial investment cost		29 601 309 EUR	29 996 017 EUR	30 053 937 EUR
Annual running cost	17 063 EUR	14 626 EUR	15 438 EUR	15 438 EUR
	13 977 EUR	13 865 EUR	15 219 EUR	45 778 EUR
	76 486 EUR	71 286 EUR	69 828 EUR	76 444 EUR
Calculation period		30	30	30
Cost of greenhouse gas emissions		99 687 EUR	72 989 EUR	65 519 EUR
Residual value		4 404 212 EUR	4 404 212 EUR	4 404 212 EUR
Discount rate		1.5 %	1.5 %	1.5 %
Estimated economic lifetime		30	30	30
Disposal cost		N/A	N/A	N/A
Global cost calculated (NPV)		30 477 806 EUR	30 657 718 EUR	30 737 336 EUR

The hybridGEOTABS systems have bigger life cycle cost (LCC) than the non-GEOTABS variant – the difference is very small, only 259 530 EUR, which is less than 1 % of the life cycle cost. This difference between Ter Potterie and other demonstration buildings can be attributed to lower insulation levels and high technology standards even in the baseline scenario, which is given by the fact that the elderly care home may have stricter comfort and IAQ requirements. The sensitivity of the results is very small (for details, see [D5.5 – Cost Benefit Analysis](#)).

It is also interesting to look at the cumulative costs of the basic scenario – this is shown in Figure 7-16, wherein the relevant costs are plotted (operation, maintenance, CO₂, energy and costs related to specific technologies for the given variant). We can see the renewal of key technologies after 15 years, as well as the fact that the costs of the hybridGEOTABS variants grow slower over time. Unlike for the other buildings in this study, the costs of the three variants do not differ much.

Figure 7-16: Ter Potterie – Cumulative costs for the basic scenario. Only costs for operation, maintenance, energies, CO₂ and technology specific investments are plotted. For comparison, a variant with photovoltaics was added (for details, see [D5.5](#)).

7.6. Conclusions

The results of the simulations of Ter Potterie show a very similar behaviour among the three scenarios. This particular case is influenced by the strong impact of the ventilation flowrates, which is reflected in the associated share in primary energy and, indirectly, in the heat recovered, which is much higher than the heat demand of the building. The *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has the lowest heat demand, followed by the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC*. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario shows the lowest cooling demand and the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario the highest cooling demand. In all scenarios, the heating demand is dominant. The CO₂ levels are not reported due to fixed high ventilation rates of the building compared to the results of the other buildings in the deliverable.

The overall space heating efficiencies are 0.98 for the *nonGEOTABS-RBC*, 1.31 for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and 1.43 for the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario. The global space cooling efficiencies are 3.45 for the *nonGEOTABS-RBC*, 8.84 for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* and 5.80 for the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario. The difference between the RBC and MPC is due to the reduced cooling demand. However, the impact of cooling is low and looking at the combined global efficiencies of heating and cooling, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* shows the highest value (1.52), while the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario has the lowest (1.07). The *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* is situated in the middle of them with an efficiency of 1.44.

The savings in primary energy use are also influenced by the impact of the ventilation, which represents around half of the primary energy and is practically invariable in all scenarios. Nevertheless, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario reduces the energy use by almost 9 % compared to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario (almost 7 % for Belgian factors), while the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* can further reduce up to 2.7 % (2 % for Belgium) over the energy use in the RBC scenario. Those percentages are higher when looking at the elements of the system that vary among the scenarios. Then, the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* shows a reduction of more than 17 % (14 % for Belgium) while the scenario with MPC control shows further savings of 5.7 % (4.5 % for Belgium) with respect to the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario.

Regarding the CO₂-emissions, the same reasoning applies. The ventilation has a large impact on the emissions, and the savings are almost 14 % (almost 27 % for Belgium) for the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario compared to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario. The *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario emits 4.5 % (10.2 % for Belgium) less CO₂ than the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC*. The savings are greater if the ventilation is removed from the analysis, with the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario having a reduction of 22.5 % (30.7 % for Belgium) compared to the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* scenario, while the MPC scenario reaches a further reduction of 8 % (12.2 % for Belgium) compared to the *hybridGEOTABS-RBC* scenario.

In terms of financial costs, the *hybridGEOTABS-MPC* scenario life cycle cost is only about 1 %, or about 260 kEUR more expensive than the *nonGEOTABS-RBC* baseline, which is not a significant difference given the uncertainties of the calculations. For Ter Potterie, the costs for the three variants are very similar.

8. Results & Conclusions

Table 7-8 shows a summary of the most representative energy and environmental KPIs of all buildings included in this deliverable. Table 7-9 shows the differences in the indicators of the different scenarios compared to the nonGEOTABS-RBC scenario of each building.

From the energy and environmental analysis, we can conclude that in all case-study buildings the hybridGEOTABS scenarios achieve lower primary energy use than the nonGEOTABS-RBC baseline scenario, and the use of MPC instead of RBC leads to additional savings. The hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario is able to achieve up to 48% of primary energy savings and 62% of CO₂-emission savings for the Haus M multi-family building. In that building, about 95% of the space heating demand and 45% of the space cooling demand are covered by GEOTABS.

Table 7-8: All buildings – Summary of energy and environmental indicators

	Haus M		Infracx			Ter Potterie		
	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC
Active injected heat [kWh/m ² /year]	49.9	39.5	9.6	10.8	13.1	12.1	12.3	14.8
Heating demand GEOTABS [kWh/m ² /year]		37.5		7.0	8.1		12.1	14.8
Heating demand nonGEOTABS [kWh/m ² /year]	49.9	2.0	9.6	3.8	5.1	12.1	0.3	0.0
Pre-heating ventilation [kWh/m ² /year]			6.3	8.5	2.0	19.9	20.6	18.0
Global share GEOTABS heating + pre-heating [-]		95%		37%	53%		37%	45%
GSHP SCOP space heating (component) [-]		3.2		3.1	5.1		6.2	5.8
Global efficiency space heating [-]	0.9 ✓	2.7	0.9	2.0 ✓	2.3	1.0	1.3 ✓	1.4
Active extracted heat [kWh/m ² /year]	25.3	13.3	18.4	14.3	21.6	3.8	3.4	2.0
Cooling demand GEOTABS [kWh/m ² /year]		5.9		14.3	21.6		3.4	2.0
Cooling demand nonGEOTABS [kWh/m ² /year]	25.3	7.4	18.4	0.0	0.0	3.8	0.0	0.0
Pre-cooling ventilation [kWh/m ² /year]			0.9	3.0	5.2	0.4	0.4	0.6
Global share GEOTABS cooling + pre-cooling [-]		45%		83%	81%		89%	77%
GSHP SCOP cooling (component) [-]		2.04		4.00				
Global efficiency space cooling [-]	✓ 4.6	2.4	3.6	5.3 ✓	7.0	3.5 ✓	8.8	5.8
Global efficiency space heating and cooling [-]	1.2 ✓	2.7	1.5	2.8 ✓	4.1	1.1	1.4 ✓	1.5
Heat recovery (heating) [kWh/m ² /year]	24.4	23.7	15.4	18.1	14.8	47.9	49.4	48.8
Heat recovery (cooling) [kWh/m ² /year]	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2
Ventilation fans [kWh/m ² /year]	1.0	1.0	3.3	4.7	0.8	17.1	17.1	17.1
Heat extracted from the ground [kWh/m ² /year]	NA	26.2	NA	14.6	9.5	NA	10.1	12.3
Heat delivered to the ground [kWh/m ² /year]	NA	9.2	NA	15.3	23.2	NA	15.3	2.6
Primary energy use (EU factor) [kWh/m ² /year]	76.4 ✓	39.9	37.7	35.3 ✓	22.0	72.8	66.3 ✓	64.5
Primary energy use (local factor) [kWh/m ² /year]	74.1 ✓	34.3	41.3	42.4 ✓	26.4	80.3	74.8 ✓	73.3
CO ₂ emissions (EU factor) [kg/m ² /year]	14.2 ✓	5.4	6.3	4.6 ✓	2.9	11.9	10.3 ✓	9.8
CO ₂ emissions (local factor) [kg/m ² /year]	12.5 ✓	1.2	4.4	1.0 ✓	0.6	8.1	6.0 ✓	5.4

Table 7-9: All buildings – Relative differences of all scenarios with the nonGEOTABS-RBC scenario as reference. In brackets, relative differences respect to the hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario

	Haus M		Infrax			Ter Potterie			
	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC	nonGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-RBC	hybridGEOTABS-MPC	
Active injected heat [kWh/m ² /year]	49.9	-21 %	9.6	+12 %	+36 % (+21 %)	12.1	+2 %	+23 %	(+20 %)
Pre-heating ventilation [kWh/m ² /year]			6.3	+35 %	-68 % (-76 %)	19.9	+4 %	-9 %	(-13 %)
Global efficiency space heating [-]	0.9	+211 %	0.9	+124 %	+167 % (+19 %)	1.0	+33 %	+46 %	(+9 %)
Active extracted heat [kWh/m ² /year]	25.3	-47 %	18.4	-22 %	+17 % (+51 %)	3.8	-10 %	-48 %	(-42 %)
Pre-cooling ventilation [kWh/m ² /year]			0.9	+225 %	+467 % (+74 %)	0.4	+2 %	+42 %	(+39 %)
Global efficiency space cooling [-]	4.6	-48 %	3.6	+50 %	+98 % (+32 %)	3.5	+156 %	+68 %	(-34 %)
Global efficiency space heating and cooling [-]	1.2	+119 %	1.5	+87 %	+173 % (+46 %)	1.1	+34 %	+41 %	(+5 %)
Heat recovery (heating) [kWh/m ² /year]	24.4	-3 %	15.4	+18 %	-4 % (-18 %)	47.9	+3 %	+2 %	(-1 %)
Heat recovery (cooling) [kWh/m ² /year]	0.3	-4 %	0.0	+1771 %	+3014 % (+66 %)	0.0	-51 %	+22332 %	(+46000 %)
Ventilation fans [kWh/m ² /year]	1.0	+0 %	3.3	+41 %	-77 % (-83 %)	17.1	+0 %	+0 %	(-0 %)
Primary energy use (EU factor) [kWh/m ² /year]	76.4	-48 %	37.7	-6 %	-42 % (-38 %)	72.8	-9 %	-11 %	(-3 %)
Primary energy use (local factor) [kWh/m ² /year]	74.1	-54 %	41.3	+3 %	-36 % (-38 %)	80.3	-7 %	-9 %	(-2 %)
CO ₂ emissions (EU factor) [kg/m ² /year]	14.2	-62 %	6.3	-27 %	-54 % (-38 %)	11.9	-14 %	-18 %	(-5 %)
CO ₂ emissions (local factor) [kg/m ² /year]	12.5	-91 %	4.4	-76 %	-85 % (-38 %)	8.1	-27 %	-34 %	(-10 %)

For the Infrax office building and Ter Potterie elderly home, the reductions achieved in the hybridGEOTABS-RBC scenario are smaller, that is around 6% and 9% of primary energy savings, and 27% and 14% of CO₂-emission savings respectively. In these buildings, about 37% of the heating demands and over 80% of the cooling demands are covered by GEOTABS. However, the Infrax office building illustrates the significant improvements (38% of additional primary energy and CO₂-emission savings) possible by use of MPC, leading up to 42% primary energy savings and 54% of CO₂-emission savings when comparing hybridGEOTABS-MPC to nonGEOTABS-RBC. The improved system control leads to an increase in the share of GEOTABS in heating and an increase in overall system efficiencies (e.g. reduced electricity use of the fans, increased SCOP of the heat pump, and overall system efficiencies).

In the Ter Potterie elderly home, at the first glance, the savings due to MPC are limited to about 3% of primary energy savings. However, considering that the MPC in that building was not allowed the same degrees of freedom as in the Infrax building, this result is not unexpected. When focussing on those parts of the system where the MPC was allowed to make a difference compared to the RBC, primary energy savings up to 21% were observed. In summary, the performance of the hybridGEOTABS system is highly influenced by the specific HVAC configuration (what part of the heating load can be covered by the GSHP) and the degrees of freedom of the controls.

The aforementioned results all assume that the electricity provided to the building represents the EU average electricity mix in 2020. The report also includes results with the local electricity mix from the country where the building is located, and a sensitivity analysis. This analysis illustrates that hybridGEOTABS buildings benefit more from an increased energy-efficiency and reduced carbon-intensity of the electricity mix. Therefore, their advantage as compared to nonGEOTABS buildings will only increase in the future.

Regarding the life-cycle cost calculations for these buildings, it was found that the hybridGEOTABS-MPC scenarios lead to an increase in life-cycle cost when compared to the nonGEOTABS-RBC, but this increase is limited to between 1% and 4.4%, which seems a small amount, especially for providing a much more environmentally friendly and comfortable building.

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